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Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures in Sweden – Detention Infrastructures

Country Dossier (WP3)

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Summary

This Country Dossier on Sweden presents an overview of the assisted and forced return migration infrastructures (RMIs) in Sweden, focusing on detention infrastructures as a case study. It examines how return migration governance is put into practice through the theoretical lenses of RMIs, which refers to the actions (*doings*) and interactions (*relations*) of actors, and the formal and informal methods, strategies, materialities—such as places, geography, and objects—as well as technologies that they deploy in the implementation of these policies.

Sweden's migration policy has undergone a significant shift since the 2015 refugee emergencies, moving from a historically generous asylum system to a restrictive approach prioritizing returns. This shift is further reinforced by the 2022 election of a centre-right coalition government with strong support from the Sweden Democrats, a right-wing populist party. The Tidö Agreement among the coalition partners has driven this hardening stance, prioritizing expanded detention, accelerated returns, and deterrence measures. Yet beneath this political rhetoric lies a complex and often inefficient governance system, where formal objectives clash with on-the-ground realities, creating ambiguities, overlaps, and implementation gaps.

A diverse network of state and non-state actors engage in facilitating, contesting, or ambiguously navigating return processes. At the heart of Sweden's RMI is the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA), which oversees detention ("return centres") and assisted returns, while the Police Authority enforces removals. These actors operate within a multilevel and multi-scalar governance framework, collaborating with EU agencies like Frontex and cooperating and coordinating with Nordic countries, and engaging in bilateral readmission agreements and informal arrangements, deploying ambulatory liaison officers to facilitate deportations. Civil society organizations play a constrained role, providing legal and psychosocial support while criticizing systemic coercion. Despite their advocacy, rights-based dissent is marginalized in favour of enforcement efficiency.

A key finding is the fluid boundary between "voluntary" and forced returns. The SMA employs motivational interviews and return counselling to pressure rejected asylum seekers into "cooperating" - framing compliance as the *only* alternative to harsher enforcement. This performative voluntariness obscures the reality that many "assisted" returns occur under structural duress. Meanwhile, Sweden's prison-like detention centres, rebranded as "return centres", rely on a dynamic security approach (staff presence over physical restraints) yet remain sites of migration control, where migrants undergo systematic preparation for removal – either *enforced voluntary return* or deportation.

Despite its centralized enforcement regime, Sweden's RMI faces significant gaps:

- Administrative inefficiencies, including bureaucratic overload and reorganization-induced delays, hinder timely returns.
- Identity verification failures stall nearly half of forced removals, compounded by 'uncooperative' origin countries.
- Soaring costs, with forced removals now 75% more expensive than in 2021.

- Ethical compromises, as vulnerable groups (minors, trauma survivors) face inadequate protections during removals.

Tensions among actors further complicate governance. While state agencies (SMA, Police, and Prison Service) collaborate through *co-location* and *data-sharing*, their enforcement-first approach clashes with CSOs' rights-based advocacy. Despite sporadic dialogue, systemic reform remains elusive, with political discourse favouring expedited removals over transparency or accountability.

Sweden's RMI exemplifies a paradox: a highly organized enforcement regime undermined by operational dysfunctions and rights violations. The emphasis on deterrence and efficiency — through detention expansion, *coercive voluntariness*, and international cooperation— has not resolved structural flaws. Instead, it has deepened ethical and practical contradictions, leaving migrants in precarious limbo while failing to deliver politically promised results. Moving forward, addressing these challenges requires a rebalancing of enforcement priorities with genuine respect for migrant rights and dignity.

Keywords: Return migration, forced returns, assisted voluntary return, detention, Sweden, coercive voluntariness, deportation infrastructure.

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- A trajectory approach, which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026), coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Brief introduction of the wider GAPs project and WP3

Return migration has become a policy priority across the world, and especially in Europe. The GAPS project is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies, and the potential disconnects between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a de-centring approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Euro-centric understanding of return policymaking. The consortium consists of 17 partners in 12 countries across four different continents¹.

This Country Dossier on Sweden is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPS project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is *put in practice* through the concept of “return migration infrastructures (RMIs)”, by focusing on the so-called “crucial meso-level” (Faist 2021). Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g. Xiang & Lindquist 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (“doings”), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape – i.e. facilitate *or* undermine and contest – the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the aforementioned work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground through a range of practices (Koinova et al. 2021).

1.2 Introduction of the case study

Sweden, once celebrated for its generous asylum policies (Fratzke, 2017; Parusel, 2024), has undergone a dramatic transformation since the watershed moment of 2015, when it welcomed tens of thousands of refugees fleeing the Syrian war with unprecedented openness. However, the so-called “long summer of migration” quickly gave way to a restrictive paradigm shift, as crisis-induced policy changes recast return—rather than protection—as the cornerstone of Sweden’s migration governance. This shift was institutionalized following the 2022 election of a centre-right coalition government backed by the populist Sweden Democrats, whose Tidö Agreement enshrined stricter border controls, expanded detention, and accelerated removals. Yet, as Henrik Malm Lindberg (2023) notes, Sweden’s return policies remain caught in a fundamental tension—balancing efficiency, legality, and humanitarian considerations (p. 152). Migrants are pressured to “cooperate” with authorities to avoid forced removal, a duality that permeates Sweden’s RMIs, where institutional checks coexist with enforcement logics.

This report examines how these contradictions unfold in practice, focusing on detention centres as micro-sites of removal—spaces where policies materialize through the interplay of actors, technologies, and coercive structures. Sweden’s RMIs operates within a centralized yet contested governance framework, where policies of deterrence, efficiency, and control shape the lived realities of migrants subjected to removal. The RMIs in Sweden relies on a complex governance framework, with the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) at its core, overseeing detention, assisted voluntary return (AVR), and enforcement. Yet, despite this centralized structure, the implementation of returns unfolds through complex, often contradictory practices—particularly within Sweden’s detention centres, which function as micro-sites of removal. These facilities, officially rebranded as “return centres”, are not merely holding

¹ For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>

spaces but active sites of governance, where migrants awaiting deportation encounter a spectrum of pressures—from coercive enforcement to "coerced voluntariness"—designed to expedite their departure.

In this report, the term “infrastructure” is utilized interchangeably with the term “governance” - specifically “governance in practice”. This encompasses the actions (*doings*), interactions (*relational doings*), and inactions (*non-doings, gaps*) of various governance actors as they seek to implement, align with, or contest specific policies. This includes a range of formal and informal *methods, strategies, materialities*—such as places, geography, and objects—as well as *technologies* employed in the implementation of these policies.

As such, this study zooms in on detention infrastructures as critical nodes in Sweden’s RMIs, examining how actors, materialities, and technologies interact to produce removal outcomes. Sweden’s detention centres reveal the disjuncture between policy intent and practice, in which state (e.g. detention staff) and non-state actors (e.g. civil society organizations, healthcare providers) together with migrants themselves negotiate, resist, or reinforce removal processes through daily interactions, creating a spectrum of coercion that blurs the line between “voluntary” and forced return.

Besides providing an overview of assisted (voluntary) return infrastructures in Sweden, the analysis focuses on three key dimensions:

- Actor Dynamics – How detention staff, SMA officers, CSOs, and healthcare providers engage in practices of persuasion, care, or control, shaping migrants’ pathways to removal.
- Materialities and Technologies – The role of documentation regimes, surveillance, and motivational interviews in facilitating returns, as well as the spatial design of detention centres as sites of immobilization.
- Coerced Voluntariness – The ways in which Sweden’s emphasis on "voluntary" compliance obscures structural pressures, with return counselling functioning as a soft enforcement tool.

By situating Sweden’s detention centres within broader debates on infrastructures and migration governance, this study challenges simplistic binaries between assisted and forced returns. Instead, it reveals how removal infrastructures operate along a continuum of coercion, where even seemingly voluntary processes are embedded in systems of constraint. Ultimately, this examination underscores how detention centres are not passive containers but active producers of removal, where policy, practice, and migrant agency collide.

Outline

The report will commence with the “methods” section. Section 3 summarises basic information about asylum and return migration trends in Sweden as well as the underlying political developments that led to the evolution of today’s return migration infrastructures. In Section 4, based on the desk research the report will outline Sweden’s RMIs, map actors and their relations. Furthermore, this section will discuss assisted (voluntary) returns, forced removals, and the concept of “voluntariness”. Section 5 will focus on the case study, and present the findings from the fieldwork in detention centres, examining the actors, their doings, materials and relationships. The conclusion will provide a systematic summary of the key findings.

2. Methods

2.1 General methodological framework of WP3

The WP3 research lasted from June 2023 to June 2024 and included two main tasks. First, creating an overview of RMIs in each partner country by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2²). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removal, and pushbacks) as a case study. The research started from a specific “entry point” on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of interviews (n=15) in each country with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, that may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees were provided an Information Letter and signed the Consent Form of participation in the research. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions, on a voluntary basis.

2.2 Specific conditions of data collection and analysis of the case study

The initial idea of this study was to focus on a single case study – either the RMIs organised around (assisted) voluntary returns or forced removals. However, during the course of our fieldwork and a more thorough examination of the data, we recognized the significant interrelation between these two domains. This realization constitutes also one of the key findings of our study: the intrinsic duality of *voluntariness* and *coercion* in the context of returns is crucial for understanding the structure of RMIs, as it elucidates their operations and interrelations. Conversely, it can also be argued that examining RMIs brings this duality to the forefront. Consequently, we opted to examine both aspects. This allowed us to explore the complex interplay of voluntary and coercive elements within Sweden's return migration infrastructure, with a specific focus on detention centres as one of the main sites for understanding RMIs.

Work Package 3 in Sweden is based on a mixed method, combining interviews with desk research on legal and policy documents issued by authorities, public inquiries, and grey literature relevant to the topic. We conducted in total 16 in-depth interviews with various stakeholders, particularly focusing on authorities and civil society organizations involved in the return migration framework. Among the key authorities interviewed were representatives from the Swedish Migration Agency and the Border Police. Within the Migration Agency, six individuals were interviewed, including an expert in return policies and staff from detention centres with diverse responsibilities. These detention centres, overseen by the Migration Agency, house migrants who have received a deportation order. The agency's responsibilities include overseeing these detentions until a return can be facilitated or until intervention by

² See further: [WP2/Legal frameworks – Working Paper Series – GAPs](#)

the Border Police is warranted. The interviews yielded valuable insights into the operational dynamics of detention and return enforcement in Sweden.

Civil society representatives interviewed included members from organizations such as the Swedish Red Cross, Save the Children, Caritas, and FARR, all of which are dedicated to protecting the rights of individuals during the return process by providing legal, social, and psychological assistance. Additionally, insights from representatives of DELMI, UNHCR, and a lawyer with experience in both civil society and legal representation for rejected asylum seekers provided valuable contributions to the analytical sections.

The interviews were conducted using a purposive sampling method, allowing participants to choose between in-person, phone, or Zoom formats. All interviews, with the exception of two conducted in person with detention centre staff, were carried out via Zoom and recorded using the platform's recording feature. The in-person interviews took place in a private office and were recorded on a mobile device. Prior to each interview, participants were provided with information regarding the study, and both verbal and written consent were obtained. In the case of interviews with staff from the detention centre, members of the research team participated in a staff meeting to present the study, allowing staff members the opportunity to voluntarily express their willingness to participate.

We visited two detention centres, where in one centre we conducted interviews only with health care personnel. It was evident that a significant layer of security measures was in place; the facility was enclosed by a cage-like fence, and our movement within the centre was restricted. We were escorted to and from the entrance. The staff exhibited a calm and friendly demeanour. Overall, they conveyed appreciation for their involvement in the study, as they often feel that decisions regarding their workplace are made without their consultation.

Table 1 - Overview of conducted interviews for GAPs WP3

Category/ type of interviewee	Number of interviews
Detention staff (D1-5)	5
Representatives of Civil Society Organisations (CSO)	6
Expert	1
Border police	1
Health care providers	2
Case officer at Migration Agency	1
SUM	16

All interview transcriptions translated into English and were coded and analysed with the help of MAXQDA, a qualitative data analysis software.

3. Context

3.1. Context of (return)migration in Sweden

Sweden has undergone significant variations in the number of immigrants, with marked increases observed during specific periods: labour immigration peaked in the late 1960s, followed by family reunification of guest workers and a surge of refugees throughout 1970s and 1980s from countries such as Chile, Ethiopia, Iran, Lebanon, Poland, Turkey, and Vietnam, and an influx from the former Yugoslavia in the early 1990s. In the 2000s, the majority of new arrivals were from Iraq and Somalia, while the 2010s saw Syrians emerge as the largest group of asylum-seekers (Åslund et al., 2017). Since 2012, asylum applications in Sweden increased gradually, culminating in a record high of 162,877 asylum applications in 2015. Although there has been a decline in numbers since the peak of 2014-2015, the overall immigration rate remains historically elevated. During this period (2022-2024), Sweden also received 72,453³ people from Ukraine following EU's Temporary Protection Directive.

Figure 1 - Asylum applications 2000-2024

Source: Migrationsverket (Swedish Migration Agency)⁴

Efforts to limit asylum applications through the introduction of new legislation about the issuance of temporary residence permits instead of permanent ones, succeeded in reducing asylum application figures from 2016 onward. By 2018, Sweden was accommodating the second-largest populations of Syrian and Somali refugees, as well as the third-largest groups of Afghan and Eritrean refugees in Europe (UNHCR, 2019). In total, by 2019, Sweden was home to over 250,000 refugees, which represented the ninth-largest ratio globally and the second highest in Europe, following Malta (UNHCR, 2020).

³ Source: Migrationsverket (<https://www.migrationsverket.se/om-migrationsverket/statistik/asyl.html>)

⁴ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/om-migrationsverket/statistik/asyl.html>

3.2 Historical overview of RMIs in Sweden

The topic of returns is not a new phenomenon in Sweden; however, it has only recently gained prominence within migration policy discourses, particularly following the 2015/2016 refugee emergencies and the subsequent series of polycrises that the country experienced. Consequently, the historical trajectory of RMIs can be examined through the lens of Sweden's evolving migration policies. RMIs took shape incrementally most often through crisis-induced adaptations and affected by policy fluctuations (e.g. reactive migration policies) and broader macroeconomic and political factors. Several pivotal non-conclusive moments can be identified in the evolution of RMIs.

The first juncture is the end of the “guest worker” regime in Sweden and other Western European countries, prompted by the economic downturn following the 1973 oil crisis. In the 1960s, Sweden welcomed guest workers from both European and non-European countries, leading to the implementation of regulations governing non-Nordic labour immigration. This resulted in the formation of the Swedish Immigration Board in 1969, which is now known as the Swedish Migration Agency, the primary governance actor in Sweden's RMI. The regulatory framework aimed to manage and curtail immigration flows. According to Thomas Hammar (1985, p.18-19) Sweden never had a similar guest worker programme of other European countries. Accordingly, Sweden “retained its belief that immigration policy should not separate the right to work from the right of residence”, which led to the country's adoption of policy of multiculturalism as integration policy in 1975.⁵ Despite the significant economic challenges posed by the 1973 oil/financial crisis, which drastically reduced the demand for guest workers, migratory movements persisted (Parusel, 2015). From the latter part of the 1970s into the 1980s, there was a notable surge in refugee immigration. The repercussions of the crisis became evident in the 1980s, as Western countries, including Sweden, governments began to implement direct measures (e.g. development assistance, investment loans, customs exemptions, and the reduction of return-related expenses, including the coverage of travel costs) to “encourage” immigrants to return to their countries of origin voluntarily (Castles & Miller, 1993; Altamirano, 1995, p. 267) but also introduced stringent measures (e.g. prolonging the process of granting permanent status to guest workers) to dissuade migrants (Hammar, 1985, p. 8).

Another critical moment of formation is Sweden's accession to the European Union in 1995 and subsequent legislative and regulatory changes introduced (cf. Schierup & Ålund, 2011). We should also note that during the 1990s Sweden again went through another wave of financial crisis and hosted more than hundred thousands of refugees from the war-torn Balkan region. In 1999, the Migration Agency assumed the primary role of enforcing return decisions and managing individuals in detention, a responsibility that had previously rested largely with the Police Authority. This shift meant that the Police Authority's role was now confined to certain categories of return (Regeringens proposition 1997/98:173, p. 35-36). The study conducted by Tollefsen Altamirano (1995) emphasizes that an explicit return policy has emerged since the 1990s, a development that was previously absent. Altamirano posits that Sweden has traditionally prioritized individual choice (*voluntariness*), with the discourse surrounding returns being predominantly initiated by individuals on a voluntary basis prior

⁵ See further the principles of *equality, freedom of choice* and *partnership* to trace the emphasis on voluntariness in Sweden's return discourses

to the 1990s. One significant factor contributing to the prioritization of return issues, as evidenced by public inquiries, is Sweden's accession to the European Union (SOU 2013:37). The introduction of the Return Directive in 2008 mandated Member States to establish standards and regulations for the return of third-country nationals residing irregularly within their borders (SOU 2009:60).

In the early 2000s, the importance of enforcing return decisions became increasingly prominent in various appropriation directives issued to the Migration Agency (Thorburn Stern & Shakra, 2024, pp-10-12). The current Aliens Act was enacted in 2006, and subsequent regulations began to intensify the discourse surrounding returns, further institutionalizing the return-related responsibilities within the Migration Agency. During this period, governments shifted their focus towards return initiatives, including enforcement (Malm-Lindberg, 2023, p. 159). A notable initiative from this period to bolster the cooperation between three authorities (SMA, the Police and Prison and Probation Service) was the government-initiated REVA project (*Rättssäkert och Effektivt Verkställighetsarbete*) which operated between 2011 and 2014 and aimed to boost the effectiveness of enforcement of deportations of persons staying in Sweden on a long-term basis without possessing the permits necessary for doing so (Thorburn Stern & Shakra, 2024, p.9).

The discourse surrounding return intensified during the refugee emergencies of 2015/2016, significantly altering the landscape of migration governance in Sweden. In November 2015, Sweden implemented temporary border controls alongside a new restrictive asylum policy, which has been characterized as a paradigm shift in the country's migration policy which was later codified through the "2016 Temporary Law" which reduced the grounds for residence permits compared to the Aliens Act, and introduced *temporary* residence permits for refugees and individuals granted subsidiary protection status as the new standard (Thorburn Stern & Shakra, 2024, pp.9-10)). Another pivotal moment occurred following the terrorist attack in Stockholm in April 2017 (EMN synthesis report 2017), which further elevated the prominence of return issues in migration policy discourse.

In addition, to enhance the efficiency of return operations and prioritize the return of rejected asylum seekers and irregular migrants, the government launched a public inquiry focused on returns. The Return Inquiry articulated that a "humane migration policy that safeguards the right to asylum" (SOU 2017:93, p.30) necessitates the prompt return of individuals with negative asylum decisions to their countries of origin. The 2017 Public Inquiry on "Return" proposed enhanced authority for the Police to employ intrusive measures during internal border control operations. These proposals were subsequently incorporated into the Aliens Act in 2021 and 2023.

The shift towards more restrictive migration policies has resulted in a further institutionalization of return processes, characterized by expanded roles for various authorities, the reorganization of existing governance structures, and improved cooperation and coordination among governmental and non-governmental entities. As a result, the Migration Agency has been granted increased authority and has taken on a coordinating role. Similarly, the Police have been empowered with enhanced capabilities to conduct internal immigration controls, including measures such as fingerprinting, body searches, and photography of individuals who have absconded and are no longer accessible to the Migration Agency. In 2020, the Swedish National Audit Office released a report (*Riksrevisionens*

rapport om återvändandeverksamheten, 2020/21: SfU6) assessing the execution of the return policy from 2013 to 2018, identifying several deficiencies in its implementation. The findings revealed that more than 50% of the 23,000 cases did not result in a documented departure. While many cases were transferred to the Police, a considerable number remained unresolved. The audit report also pointed out insufficient collaboration among government agencies, rising costs, unmet policy objectives, a lack of comprehensive perspective, and conflicting priorities between the demands of return operations and other regulations that serve different purposes.

In the general elections held in September 2022, a centre-right coalition, bolstered by the right-wing populist party known as the Sweden Democrats, secured a majority. Subsequently, in late 2022, this coalition, along with its supporting far-right party (Sweden's Democrats), unveiled an extensive reform initiative referred to as the Tidö Agreement, which explicitly identifies return as a key priority, advocating for enhanced detention measures and various restrictions on freedom of movement to ensure the enforcement of return decisions. Following the Tidö Agreement, the government has launched a public inquiry through directive (Dir. 2023:151) aimed at reassessing the incentive mechanisms (return grants) for voluntary repatriations. Furthermore, another inquiry has been established to explore strategies for increasing repatriation among long-term residents of Sweden who have not successfully integrated into the societal fabric, particularly in terms of employment, language proficiency, and cultural assimilation (Government, 26 October 2023).⁶

Box 1 - Paradigm shift in Sweden's migration policy and RMIs

In a press release dated 12 September 2024, the Swedish government reiterated its new migration policy within the framework of the 2025 budget bill. The government characterized this policy as encompassing “reforms for a responsible and restrictive migration policy”. They asserted that a “paradigm shift” in migration policy is currently underway, a development that is celebrated and rationalized by highlighting the lowest number of asylum seekers in Sweden since 1997. The government views this trend as “moving in the right direction” (ibid.). To enhance the migration field, the government announced a budgetary increase of SEK 513 million for 2025, SEK 2,559 million for 2026, and SEK 1,357 million for 2027. These funds are intended to establish a more efficient reception and return system, which includes the expansion of both internal and external migration controls, initiatives to combat fraud and abuse in asylum claims, and efforts to promote voluntary repatriation (e.g. a significant increase in the “repatriation grant”, additional funds to SMA for information campaigns). A portion of this budget will also be allocated for the construction of new detention centres and the expansion of existing facilities, and for strengthening the work of the Migration Agency’s role by expanding their capacity to

⁶ In another directive (Dir. 2023:129), the government initiated a public investigation focused on tightening the procedures for acquiring citizenship, aligning with the government's deterring migrants. Some other notable directives and inquiries which have been initiated are: the public inquiry (SOU 2024:10) “Limitation period for removal orders and certain issues related to re-entry bans”; Dir. (2023:149). “State inquiry into higher requirements for qualifying for welfare benefits for new arrivals and non-citizens”; Dir. “2023:158) “Stricter requirements for a honourable way of living and increased possibilities for revocation of residence permits”; Dir. (2023:119) “Modern and appropriate rules for detention”; Dir. (2023:137) “Adaptation of Swedish regulations for granting asylum and the asylum procedure according to EU law’s minimum standards”.

handle biometric data, the Police work on internal migration controls, and for the establishment of a national coordinator.

Figure 2- Swedish Government's website 2024.

In the same way, the communication conveyed in the press release released by the Government (Regeringen, 28 February 2023) employs a top-down, authoritative tone, aimed at delivering a strong policy “signal” to migrants both within Sweden and internationally, reflecting the concept of a “paradigm shift”. Similarly, the infographics featured on the government’s website (above) succinctly represent Sweden’s new, stringent migration policy. The selected iconographies underscore a rigid and uncompromising stance on asylum applications, incorporating punitive measures that indirectly perpetuate a narrative portraying migrant as potential societal threats. This approach effectively dehumanizes migrants, treating them as mere *deportable* objects, while potentially minimizing the complexities and difficulties inherent in coerced returns.

This section provided a contextual overview of the development of RMIs in Sweden. As previously noted, RMIs are influenced by shifts in migration policies, albeit in a gradual manner. The growing emphasis on returns in migration policy discourses contributes to the further institutionalization of this area.

3.3 Return migration: trends and figures

Data regarding returns is not easy to grasp⁷. While such data can provide insights, it simultaneously conceals numerous uncertainties. The intricacies of return data complicate the ability to draw definitive conclusions.

In Sweden, SMA is responsible for the collection and consolidation of return-related data. However, this information is not readily accessible on the SMA's website. Individuals seeking data on returns must either reach out to SMA officials or sift through various reports, such as the SMA's annual reports and compare it with data from the Police and Prison and Probation Services, to obtain relevant information. The complexity of the data is further exacerbated by the existence of various categorization systems and the discrepancy of the "Sweden's return data" on Eurostat⁸ and the numbers provided in SMA's annual reports. A few guiding principles have been identified that may assist in navigating the complexities of return-related data.

- Technically, a *return case* is registered by the SMA (Migrationsverket, Årsredovisning 2023) when the decision on rejection or deportation becomes enforceable, which usually happens when it becomes final. For example, SMA registered 18,523 new return cases in 2020; 14,198 in 2021; 11,580 in 2022 and 12,349 cases in 2023. The SMA and the Police have a significant backlog of open return cases, totalling nearly 47,000 cases by the end of 2020. Many cases are not completed due to time-barring or individuals absconding. The data indicates a decline in the number of registered return cases, decreasing from 18,523 in 2020 to 12,349 in 2023. This trend corresponds with a reduction in the number of "return decisions on negative asylum applications" as illustrated in Figure 3.

	2021	2022	2023
Self-managed returned	7238	6440	6630
Delegated to the police (absconded)	4028	3632	3871
Delegated to the police (coercion)	1402	1008	1010
Written off etc.	5259	7495	5748
Total closed return-cases	17,927	18,575	17,259
Open – active return cases	9,496	7,975	5,406
Open – inactive return cases	15,360	10,980	8,490

⁷ A similar observation was mentioned to us by our external reviewer, Henrik Malm Lindberg (Delmi) who led a similar research and published the Delmi report (2020:1) "Those who cannot stay: Implementing return policy in Sweden".

⁸ To give an example, the numbers for "Third-country nationals ordered to leave - annual data" on Eurostat (Sweden dataset) do not match the numbers we gathered from the SMA's annual reports and received from SMA officers. According to Eurostat, in 2021, 14,470 persons received return orders; in 2022, 14,890 persons; and in 2023, 13,840 persons. However, the data provided by the SMA shows different numbers: 7,552 persons in 2021, 8,045 in 2022, and 6,901 in 2023.

Table 2 - Swedish Migration Agency's open and closed return-cases 2021-2023. Source: Compiled from Migrationsverket, Årsredovisning 2023, p.81-85

- SMA's performance indicator is the *return rate*, which is the ratio between the number of return cases concluded due to voluntary return (in accordance with the return decision or before it has become legally binding) and the number of new return cases during the same period. SMA's return rate for 2023 was 44 percent, which was on par with the previous years (44 percent in 2022 and 43 percent in 2021) (Migrationsverket, Årsredovisning 2023, p.81)
- The number of open return cases at the end of the year decreased by 27 percent compared to 2022. The proportion of pending cases was 61 percent, which was slightly higher than in previous years. A large proportion of open active return cases concern persons who are citizens of countries that do not accept forced return. This also complicates the work of voluntary return (ibid.)
- Notably, nearly 40 percent of these cases involved migrants organizing their own departure (ibid.). This pattern has been consistent over the years, with a significant proportion of returns categorized as 'voluntary returns'.
- According to the numbers indicated in Figure 4, the proportion of exits (in all forms) appears to be relatively high in relation to the number of return cases opened per year. These figures suggest a different ratio compared to the European Commission's statement that only ca. 20 percent of individuals return after receiving a return order.
- The most common reason why the decisions are not executed is that the cases are time-barred. A large proportion of the SMA's cases are not active. This is because the person leaving the country can apply for a stay of execution and temporary residence permits. A majority of Police cases concern persons who have absconded (ibid.).
- In 2020, the SMA transferred slightly more than 50% of its return cases to law enforcement authorities. Among these cases, 55% involved individuals who had absconded, while 45% pertained to enforcement actions taken by force. Notably, half of the cases referred to the Police were beyond the statute of limitations. Regarding cases that concluded with an exit from the country, the SMA executed the majority, accounting for 70% of such instances, indicating that these individuals left 'voluntarily'. Conversely, the remaining individuals who departed from Sweden were subjected to enforcement by the Police, with approximately half of them arranging their own travel. Despite the self-arranged departures, these instances are classified as "enforced by force" due to the initial referral of the cases to the Police (Stadskontoret 2022, p.38).
- Table 2 presents the information regarding open and closed return cases from 2021 to 2023 (SMA Årsredovisning 2023). The figures for self-managed voluntary returns and cases assigned to the police appear to have reached a stable trend, with self-managed returns accounting for roughly 40 percent of the total closed cases.
- In 2023, asylum applications fell to their lowest point, with only 9,234 submissions recorded. This consistent decline can be attributed to the restrictive policies implemented since 2016.
- Figure 3 (below) illustrates that the volume of assisted forced returns remains minimal when compared to the total number of return cases. The predominant categories of actual returns over the years depicted in the chart are non-assisted (or self-managed) and

assisted voluntary returns. Furthermore, there is no notable variation in the rates of assisted voluntary returns in comparison to non-assisted voluntary returns.

Figure 3 - Return data 2015-2023. Source: Migrationsverket (Adopted from Thorburn Stern & Shakra 2024)

Third country nationals returned from Sweden following an order to leave

2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
9,695	10,160	6,845	6,850	6,425	4,930	6,805	8,615	7,670

Source: Eurostat Database (https://doi.org/10.2908/MIGR_EIRTN)⁹

- From 2015 to 2023, the cumulative data indicates that SMA processed a total of 331,411 asylum applications, with 161,578 resulting in negative outcomes. Over the same timeframe, a total of 169,919 individuals were returned, encompassing all categories of return, which represents approximately 54 percent of the total asylum applications submitted during this period. When taking into account the ongoing active and inactive cases from prior years, this percentage is marginally lower than the initial calculation.

⁹ The same discrepancy occurs in the number of “returned” third-country nationals (TCNs). To verify the accuracy of the Eurostat data, we compared it with the SMA data, where we totalled assisted voluntary returns, assisted forced returns, and non-assisted voluntary returns.

Nevertheless, this statistic reveals that nearly half of the asylum seekers left Sweden, either returning to their countries of origin or relocating to a third country.

- These figures only include cases registered with the SMA. They do not account for irregular migrants who never registered with Swedish authorities. As our reviewer H.M. Lindberg noted during our discussion (2025), the Police's executed returns also include cases where individuals never applied for asylum or any residence permit, and thus were never recorded in SMA's system.

The lack of reliable and representative data on returns poses a fundamental challenge to Sweden's return infrastructure. Without accurate information, policies designed to enhance efficiency risk being misguided or even counterproductive, potentially leading to wasted resources, rights violations, and systemic inefficiencies. In Sweden, this data gap is particularly concerning given the country's increasingly enforcement-driven approach to returns. Official statistics often fail to capture the complex realities of coerced "voluntary" returns, the true costs of detention and removals, or the outcomes for returnees. This section examined Sweden's return data landscape, highlighting critical gaps in monitoring, reporting, and evaluation that undermine the system's effectiveness and accountability. The disconnect between available data and on-the-ground realities raises serious questions about whether current policies are achieving their intended objectives or merely creating an illusion of control.

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in Sweden

Sweden's return migration framework, while appearing intricate due to the involvement of various ministries and agencies, and its domestic and international dimensions, is fundamentally centralized and primarily organized around the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA). The inherent duality of coercion versus voluntariness has significantly influenced the institutional landscape, the positioning of governance actors, and the range of actions, methodologies, and resources employed.

In this context, four distinct categories of return practices can be identified along a "voluntariness spectrum" (Figure 5): 1) voluntary repatriations (for individuals holding a residence permit), 2) self-managed/non-assisted returns (*självmant återvändande*), 3) a type akin to assisted voluntary returns (for individuals who accept rejection decisions and 'cooperate' with authorities), and 4) forced removals, which can be further classified into escorted and unescorted removals. It is important to note that these categories are not mutually exclusive, leading to the use of a Venn diagram to illustrate the interrelatedness of these different types. The central theme across these categories is voluntariness, with the degree of a migrant's 'voluntary' decision to return being a critical aspect that warrants further exploration. Each category encompasses its own subtypes, shaped by varying regulations and requirements, with a predominant focus on voluntary returns as indicated by return statistics.

Voluntary repatriation pertains to the return of individuals who are legally residing in Sweden, thus positioned at the outermost edge of the voluntariness spectrum. The government offers re-establishment support and additional benefits in exchange for the relinquishment of the individual's legal residency rights. This is not specifically included in this study – except for re-establishment grants in support schemes (see page 40).

The second category, **self-managed returns**, applies to individuals who have received a rejection or expulsion order but are permitted to arrange their own departure from Sweden using personal resources. This option primarily targets complex cases where involuntary returns are not feasible - particularly when countries of origin refuse to accept forced repatriations. The category also encompasses all non-assisted voluntary returns, including cases following either negative asylum decisions or withdrawn applications.

Figure 4 - Voluntariness spectrum and return types (Source: Authors)

The third model, **assisted voluntary returns**, is part of the Swedish return system, which refers to cases where the SMA provide practical and financial support to an individual to implement a return decision. Nevertheless, in the Swedish return terminology, the term “Assisted Voluntary Returns” (AVR) is not translated literally (as *assisterad frivillig återvändande*). As shown in Figure 1, we have positioned AVR between voluntary and coerced returns, and refer to this category as *enforced voluntary returns*. This term encapsulates a condition in which a legal determination regarding expulsion results in the exclusion of a rejected asylum seeker from all formal socio-economic, educational, and health systems. Under these conditions, a return is deemed voluntary, as articulated by Venessa Baker (2018), who argues that the Swedish social welfare state establishes a punitive framework that differentiates between those who are integrated into the system and those who are marginalized.

The final category in our framework is **coerced returns**, covering both escorted/unescorted removals, known in Swedish as *utvisning*. These returns may take place within a detention facility or when the Police Authority assumes responsibility for return cases from the SMA. As mentioned above, there are overlapping elements present across all four types. Even in instances of coerced returns, law enforcement agencies often attempt to engage rejected asylum seekers in a cooperative dialogue, encouraging them to depart voluntarily. However, these non-assisted voluntary exits are counted as forced removals in return statistics.

Pushbacks, as understood in the context of illegal pushback practices taking place on Schengen borders, is not a relevant category for Sweden's return framework; however, Swedish border force do return individuals attempting to enter the country without valid travel documentation according to Chapter 8 of the Aliens Act. The Police Authority has published data on its website under the section "polisavisningar vid yttre gräns", which details the number of rejections at Sweden's entry points from non-European Union (EU) or European Economic Area (EEA) nations. Typically, these individuals are placed on return flights. The Police Authority indicates that internal border controls in other Schengen nations involve only random checks. The Police Authority firmly denies the occurrence of illegal pushbacks at the Swedish border or within its jurisdiction (Torbjörn-Stern & Shakra, 2024).

The return infrastructures illustrated in Figure 5 (below) present a complex landscape due to the multiplicity of actors involved, the overlapping nature of their roles and processes, and the conditional aspects of each return trajectory. Despite this complexity, return actions are fundamentally structured around the dual principles of voluntariness and coercion that are inherent in Sweden's return and readmission policies. This duality effectively delineates the various types of returns (as specified in Figure 4) and the roles of governance actors, which may either align with or contest one another.

In this section, we will first commence with providing an overview of the return landscape by looking more closely at state and non-state actors involved. Thereafter, we will examine assisted (voluntary) returns and forced removals.

Figure 5 - Overview of Return infrastructures in Sweden

4.1 An Overview of RMI actors and their doings

The Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) occupies a central position among the actors involved in the return process, reflecting its pivotal governance role. The domestic institutional infrastructures include key governmental actors such as the Police Authority, the Prison and Probation Service, Migration Courts, the Ministry of Justice, and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (through Swedish embassies), alongside operational entities like SIDA and Return Liaison Officers. Externally, the infrastructures include Frontex, IOM, and diplomatic missions from various countries, international organizations like IOM-Finland. Non-governmental participation is represented by civil society organizations (e.g., the Red Cross, Caritas, FARR, and Stockholm Stadmission), healthcare providers, lawyers. However, as this report later details, return operations remain fundamentally state-driven, focused on enforcing legal decisions on asylum applications. Consequently, non-governmental actors operate within constrained parameters, their involvement largely restricted to providing returnee support services rather than influencing policy or decision-making processes.

As for “doings” of the aforementioned governance actors, the report emphasizes the concept of “return counselling”, offering an in-depth analysis of various interview types, techniques, and incentives utilized by case officers. Additionally, it underscores supervision and detention as two structured approaches for implementing return decisions, thereby facilitating migrants’ transition towards voluntary departure. Beyond these focal points, the report elaborates on the idea of voluntariness and the collaborative mindset that often bypasses motivational discussions. These elements are deemed crucial for enhancing the comprehension of RMIs, particularly through the examination of the methods, techniques, and strategies employed in promoting voluntary returns.

Swedish Migration Agency

SMA serves as the principal governance body overseeing the entire asylum process and is the key authority in matters related to return decisions and operations. In 1998, the Swedish Parliament (*Riksdag*) restructured the agency’s responsibilities to enhance its operational efficiency. Following this reform, the SMA was designated as the primary entity responsible for both the determination and enforcement of removal decisions (Regeringens proposition 1997/98:173, p. 35-36).

The regulatory framework governing returns in Sweden is primarily established by the Aliens Act (2005) and the Return Directive (2008). The new EU Pact on Migration and Asylum, which was approved in 2024, does not completely replace the Return Directive but introduces significant changes that modify and complement it.¹⁰ At the time of writing this a new proposal for establishing a [common system for the return of third-country nationals staying illegally in the European Union](#) was prepared by the EC (11 March 2025).

The operations of the SMA are guided by various laws, regulations, and annual appropriation directives issued by the government. The agency plays a multifaceted role in migration governance (see Box 2).

¹⁰ The Pact includes several new initiatives that are now implemented inside the Agencies: a new Screening and Border Procedures Regulation, which strengthens the enforcement of returns and speeds up asylum processing at the borders. Additionally, a new Asylum and Migration Management Regulation (AMMR) replaces the Dublin Regulation. Moreover, Frontex will have a stronger role in coordinating and executing returns, including funding “return flights” and supporting Member States in enforcing deportations (H.M. Lindberg, 2025, *informal talk*).

Box 2 - SMA's multifaceted role in migration governance

The SMA is led by a Director General, who is appointed by the government. Its operational framework is divided into three regions and the National Operations Department (NOA). The head office comprises an operations management team and authority staff, along with five departments that provide essential support for operational activities. In 2021, the administrative budget for the SMA amounted to SEK 4.4 billion. In the previous year, the agency employed approximately 6,000 individuals, equating to around 5,000 full-time equivalents (Stadskontoret, 2022, p.48).

The Ordinance¹¹ (2019:502) delineates the SMA's responsibilities, which encompass the management of residence permits, work permits, rights of residence, visas, the reception of asylum seekers, the referral of unaccompanied minors and new arrivals, as well as voluntary return, citizenship, and repatriation. Section 9 of this Ordinance specifies the SMA's role as a coordinator, mandating the agency to establish detailed cooperation agreements with the Government Offices of Sweden (Ministry for Foreign Affairs) regarding migration activities conducted by foreign authorities (Ordinance 2019:1177). Additionally, Section 10 (Ordinance 2019:1177) requires the SMA to foster international collaboration, share experiences that enhance its operations, support migration-related development initiatives, and engage in global efforts to bolster the migration capacities of countries of origin, transit, and destination. The external dimension of the SMA's responsibilities is further emphasized by Section 6 of Ordinance (2022: 1070), which empowers the agency to negotiate and enter into agreements with the International Organization for Migration (IOM) concerning resettlement and return initiatives.

Over time, the role of the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) has evolved significantly. It now functions not only as an authoritative body for decision-making in matters of asylum, visas, and citizenship but also as an operational entity overseeing reception and return centres, commonly referred to as detention centres. The agency collaborates with various public authorities and international organizations, while also organizing missions abroad aimed at managing migration and facilitating the return of individuals.

In practical terms, the SMA is responsible for managing voluntary returns, whereas the Police handle cases of forced returns. Should an individual abscond or if coercive measures are necessary, the SMA has the authority to transfer such cases to the Police, as stipulated in the Aliens Act (2005:716, Ch. 12, Sec.14). Thus, a significant aspect of the SMA's responsibilities includes providing support to the Police in these scenarios, in alignment with broader migration policy goals.¹²

Furthermore, the agency is charged with enforcing detention orders issued by both itself and the Police.¹³ This entails oversight of the detention centres and the execution of appropriate detention activities.¹⁴ In specific instances, the SMA may place detainees in prisons, remand

¹¹ In Swedish law, ordinances are a form of secondary legislation that regulate certain matters. They are enacted by the Government and set out rules that govern society and public authorities (Factsheet, Ministry of Justice Ju16.03e).

¹² 2 § Förordning (2019:502) med instruktion för Migrationsverket

¹³ 10 kap. 18 § Alience Act (2005:716).

¹⁴ 3 § 4 p. förordning (2019:502) med instruktion för Migrationsverket.

centres, or police custody.¹⁵ Within the context of the detention centres, the agency is also responsible for the transportation of detainees (e.g. to hospitals, embassies based on a risk assessment). Additionally, the SMA determines the re-establishment support for individuals opting for voluntary return and oversees support measures within the European Return and Reintegration Network (ERRIN, now known as EURP).¹⁶ The agency also monitors forced returns, actively participating in operations conducted by the Police and Frontex to ensure adherence to established procedures.¹⁷

Doings

This section examines SMA's *formal* procedures as outlined on its official website. It is crucial to emphasize that our analysis presents the agency's *prescribed* processes—not their practical implementation, nor the lived experiences of migrants navigating these requirements. The procedures vary significantly depending on the returnee's status, age, and other circumstances. For instance, unaccompanied minors follow a distinct protocol, while persons with disabilities may access specialized support structures unavailable to others (H.M. Lindberg, 2025, *pers. comm.*).

Although these steps represent standardized guidelines, street-level bureaucrats exercise considerable discretion in their enforcement. As demonstrated in Delmi (2020:1), such discretion creates variations in policy implementation, shaped by frontline workers' individual judgments and situational factors. While this report acknowledges these implementation nuances, its primary focus remains on detention infrastructures (see Section 5), rather than a comprehensive analysis of all return types.

The process will be outlined under three subheadings: a) Initial Notification (Post-Rejection), b) Return Planning Phase, and c) Pre-Departure. While this section covers the first phase and partially the second, the latter phases will be explored in greater detail in the sections on "Assisted Voluntary Return" (Section 4.2) and "Detention Infrastructures" (Section 5). That said, many of the SMA's *doings* described in these sections overlap across different phases. There is no clear-cut division, largely due to the continuous interplay between coercion and voluntariness that shapes Sweden's return migration infrastructure.

1. *Initial notification (Post-Rejection)*: The primary objective of the SMA is to facilitate what is termed a voluntary return, wherein the migrant actively chooses to return to their country of origin. As soon as a person receives rejection for an asylum claim, the person is called for a *notification interview*. This procedural meeting serves to inform the applicant of the formal outcome regarding their asylum claim and to discuss the different pathways that he/she can take. The person is informed about his/her legal right to appeal SMA's decision. Should the individual express a desire to appeal, SMA case officers are tasked with employing persuasive techniques to encourage the rejected applicant to accept the decision while also providing essential information about the appeal process. This includes sharing statistics on the success rates of appeals in comparable cases. If the applicant opts to cooperate—interpreted as "accepting the decision"—and subsequently returns "voluntarily", it is presumed that the notification interview has achieved its intended purpose, and the person is requested to sign a

¹⁵ 10 kap. 20 § utlänningslagen (2005:716).

¹⁶ 1 § förordning (2008:778) om återetableringsstöd för vissa utlänningar.

¹⁷ 12 § 2 p. förordning (2019:502) med instruktion för Migrationsverket.

so-called “*declaration of satisfaction*” (DoS)¹⁸. Once the person has signed a DoS, he/she cannot appeal the decision and must plan the return journey home.¹⁹ Formally, a DoS cannot be withdrawn, and it does not in itself constitute an authorisation to enforce the decision. However, it is assumed that an enforcement procedure will be initiated, usually with a view to immediate enforcement (Ch. 12, Sec. 7, 2.1 of the Aliens Act). Voluntary return is naturally the most obvious option when the ‘foreign national’ has given a DoS (*Migrationsverket Handboken i migrationsärenden*, 2019).

The rejection decision states the time frame for appeal, often three weeks from the day the decision was announced. SMA on its website and in notification interviews explains the “low chances” of challenging the rejection decision with the aim of convincing the person to plan return (e.g., in the notification interviews and counselling sessions, case officers use *SMA statistics to show <5% success rate*). If the person chooses to file an appeal with the Migration Court, thereby obstructing enforcement in accordance with the Aliens Act (Ch. 12, § 8), the SMA assumes the role of the opposing party, defending its stance with a well-prepared team of SMA lawyers. If the appeal is dismissed by both the Migration Court and the Migration Court of Appeal, the decision becomes legally binding, and the individual is expected to return voluntarily to their country of origin within four weeks.²⁰ While waiting for the result of the appeal, the person has the right to stay legally in Sweden. However, if the appeal is about a SMA decision marked as “to be implemented immediately” (*avvisning som ska genomföras omedelbart*²¹), the person is not allowed to stay in Sweden while waiting for the court to hear the appeal. Here the court can announce that the SMA’s rejection decision should be suspended while waiting for the appeal to be heard. If the court decides not to cancel SMA’s rejection, the person legally must leave Sweden *immediately*. It then falls upon the individual to arrange for travel and identity documentation. Once the deadline has lapsed, the individual forfeits any rights to accommodation, financial assistance, or legal residency in Sweden. Failure to depart within the stipulated timeframe results in a ban on re-entry to all Schengen countries.

Upon notification of a rejection or deportation decision, individuals are allotted varying timeframes to exit Sweden: two weeks in the case of rejection and four weeks for expulsion. In exceptional circumstances, individuals may be granted an extension beyond these standard periods. The countdown begins once the decision has attained legal effect, meaning the point at which appeals are no longer permissible. Subsequently, the SMA is tasked with conducting “return interviews” with the individual slated for return, offering support and information regarding the return process and the assistance available from the authority.

2. Return planning phase: If it is a final decision (72-hour to 4-week window for departure after final decision), the person will be called to a meeting (“return interview”) with a case officer at the SMA to plan the return. In this meeting, case officers provide information about which options are available and answer questions with a focus on travel arrangements and

¹⁸ The rules on DoS are set out in the Aliens Act (Ch. 15, Sect. 1-3). of A DoS means that the ‘alien’ (as stated in the Act) refrains from appealing against the rejection or expulsion decision.

¹⁹ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Privatpersoner/Lamna-Sverige/Avslag-pa-ansokan-om-asyl.html>

²⁰ Migrationsverket 2019, Återvända självmant när du har fått avslag på din ansökan om asyl

²¹ According to the SMA, if it is clear that there are no grounds for asylum, or any other reason for a residence permit in Sweden, the applicant receives a decision on rejection that must be implemented immediately. Such a decision is given if SMA decides on the application within three months.

deadlines. Some migrants plan to leave Sweden on their own before they have been called to return, in that case they are asked to visit the nearest SMA reception unit to get an “**exit certificate**” which needs to be handed in at a Swedish passport control when they leave the country. Should the individual decline to return ‘voluntarily’, SMA case officers evaluate the potential for additional counselling sessions to influence their decision or determine if detention is warranted. If voluntary return cannot be facilitated, the individual may either be detained or the case may be transferred to the police for enforcement actions.²²

3. *Pre-departure phase*: During return counselling sessions, case officers inform individuals about the option to stay at a designated “return centre” while preparing for departure. While Swedish law permits rejected asylum seekers to choose between residing at a return centre or in private accommodation until departure, case workers assess and recommend placement options during these interviews (as discussed in detail later). At the return centre, the counselling meetings continue and migrants receive advice and support to prepare their return (see Section 5).

Upon the expulsion decision comes into legal force, the person is obliged to hand back the so-called “Asylum Seeker card” (LMA-kort) to the SMA before leaving Sweden. If the person has been given a bank card from the SMA, he/she must withdraw the money from the account and hand the card back. If the person has been staying in an accommodation provided by the SMA, the person must vacate the accommodation and hand back the keys (ibid.). SMA has recently started cooperating more closely with the Swedish Tax Office (Skatteverket) to facilitate these de-registration procedures as well as for getting more information about the person who received a rejection decision or expulsion order.

The person has the same right to healthcare up until the day he/she leaves the country as previously, but the person will not receive any financial assistance for medicines and care after the decision has acquired legal force – only limited to emergency healthcare. As for the schooling, only children have the right to go to school as long as they remain in Sweden.²³

SMA also asks the rejected asylum seekers to obtain some “important documents when returning”²⁴, such as a register extract from the Swedish Tax Agency about a child born in Sweden; an extract from the Police Authority’s criminal records; all grades and certificates related to education, a health certificate. SMA, in certain cases provide help with translations.

‘Non-deportables’ – enforcing ‘voluntariness’

Practical obstacles may impede an individual's return following a rejection decision, such as being a minor without a guardian, the absence of a readmission agreement with the relevant country, inadequate reception systems in the home country, the individual's unwillingness to secure a valid travel document, or the reluctance of foreign authorities to issue travel documents and verify the individual's identity.²⁵

²² SMA (2023): <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Privatpersoner/Lamna-Sverige/Avslag-pa-ansokan-om-asyl.html>

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/English/Private-individuals/Leaving-Sweden/Rejection-of-application-for-asylum/Important-documents-when-returning.html>

²⁵ Migrationsverket (Frequently asked questions- <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Aktuellt/Migrationsverket-svarar/Migrationsverket-svarar/2023-05-04-Migrationsverket-svarar-hur-manga-aker-tillbaka-till-sitt-hemland.html>)

In such scenarios, a quasi-return mechanism known as "self-managed returns" is established. This approach is particularly relevant in instances where the SMA is unable to enforce return decisions to certain countries. The inability to implement these decisions compels authorities to promote what SMA refers to as 'self-managed return'. For a voluntary return to materialize, the individual must 'accept/cooperate' the return decision. Should the 'rejected asylum seeker' does not cooperate following a definitive deportation or expulsion order, the SMA is compelled to transfer the case to law enforcement. Consequently, this may result in the 'rejected asylum seekers' remaining in Sweden, despite the deportation or expulsion order, as the country of origin, which is obligated to accept its nationals, may only agree to accept individuals who return voluntarily (for instance, countries like Iran and Cuba). To address this predicament, SMA case officers actively encourage individuals with rejection decisions to consider voluntarily return. A key prerequisite for facilitating voluntary return is that "the foreign national has an attitude that does not prevent a return" (Migrationsverket, 2019, p.39)²⁶. This necessitates that case officers assess the returnee's disposition (*willingness to cooperate*) to determine if it poses an obstacle to their return. In this context, cooperation entails the individual acknowledging the rejection decision, obtaining necessary identity documents, and agreeing to return voluntarily.

SMA's soft power techniques – return counselling²⁷

SMA employs various soft power strategies, particularly through return counselling, which is best characterized as a procedural activity, wherein SMA's case officers play an active role throughout all phases of the return process. Our analysis has identified three distinct forms of communication, each labelled differently, yet utilized at various stages of return operations. It is important to recognize that these interactions occur within an asymmetric framework, wherein migrants progressively forfeit their formal rights and, consequently, their power. Initially, during the notification meeting, the rejected asylum seeker retains the right to contest the decisions made by SMA or the migration court via an appeal process. If both the Migration Court and the Migration Court of Appeal reject the appeal, the decision then attains legal validity.

²⁶ Migrationsverket, *Handläggning av återvändandearärenden i Handbok i migrationsärenden*, 2019, p.39

²⁷ Return counselling has emerged as a key focus area for the SMA. A significant event illustrating this commitment was the EMN-REG Workshop on Return Counselling, which took place in Stockholm in April 2023. This workshop was organized by the SMA in collaboration with EMN-REG, the expert group on return within the European Migration Network, among other stakeholders. Through its involvement in the EU project Capacity Development and Training for Return Counsellors (CADRE), the SMA has developed a nationally tailored training program aimed at enhancing the quality of its return counselling services. In 2023, 14 employees from the agency completed this training. Additionally, the SMA has played a role in Frontex's training initiative for return counselling by contributing to the development of the training curriculum and supplying five trainers (SMA, *Årsredovisning 2023*, p.86).

Figure 6 - Three types of interviews (Source: Authors)

Return counselling is a structured yet contested process aimed at ensuring compliance. As illustrated in Figure 6, following the issuance of a legally binding rejection or expulsion decision, the SMA conducts what are referred to as return interviews, or "*motivational interviews*". During these sessions, the SMA case officers determine the course of action based on their assessment of whether the individual who has received the rejection is willing to accept the decision and collaborate with the authorities regarding their return. These interviews are significant as they can lead to various outcomes, yet they often lack transparency. This lack of clarity fosters an informality in which the legal decision regarding the asylum application is communicated in a "semi-informal" manner. According to the SMA, the number of counselling meetings at the Agency or the Swedish Police Authority depend on "the number needed to enforce the return decision or the circumstances of the return" (EMN, 2023, p. 64). In Swedish, these sessions are termed *motiverande samtal*, which translates to "motivational interviewing" (or talks²⁸). The dialogue typically involves one party employing soft power techniques to persuade the other. Conducted within the SMA's facilities, these interviews generally involve the case officer outlining the procedures and presenting the rejected asylum seekers with options and their potential consequences. The nature of the conversation tends to be predominantly one-sided, with the rejected individual primarily engaging through questions. Caseworkers use open-ended questions to encourage voluntary return, such as discussing luggage or flight details (MV-1). As we later discuss in detention infrastructures, detention staff interviewed criticized inefficient techniques used in these interviews and underlined the importance of "*clear communication without false hope*" (D1). Given this context, the inherent asymmetry in the relationship makes it unlikely for a rejected asylum seeker to effectively contest the negative asylum decision. At this juncture, the SMA presents the individual with two options: to either cooperate and return "voluntarily" or face

²⁸ The Swedish word *samtal* which among others could also be translated as a dialogue or a talk, acknowledging the plurality of persons involved in the talk.

detention and forced deportation. Lawyers and CSOs interviewed argue interviews lack legal support, leaving migrants vulnerable to pressure. The absence of public counsellors in interviews exacerbates power imbalances (L1).

Enforcing voluntariness via fostering a collaborative attitude

The SMA identifies three critical prerequisites²⁹ necessary for facilitating the return of an individual to their home country or another country. These prerequisites include the individual's acceptance or at least non-opposition to the decision (*attitude*), a clear identification of the individual (*identity*), and their availability to the authorities (*availability*). These elements are vital for understanding how *voluntariness* is constructed through the counselling sessions, and the persuasion strategies employed by SMA case officers.

To ensure compliance, authorities possess various mechanisms to influence the individual's *attitude*. These mechanisms encompass early provision of information regarding potential decisions, clarity about the implications of different outcomes, and the conduct of investigative and motivational interviews. This approach aligns with the first prerequisite, which aims to foster a "collaborative attitude". The strategies employed include not only soft power techniques, primarily utilized in motivational interviews, but also a range of supportive and punitive measures that reflect a carrot-and-stick approach. For instance, the SMA may reduce the daily allowance (referred to as LMA-kort) for individuals without children or use the threat of imposing a re-entry ban on those who fail to comply with the decision. Such a re-entry ban can serve as a significant deterrent for individuals wishing to return to Sweden (or any other Schengen country) after their asylum application has been denied, particularly if they intend to apply for a work permit or visit family members in the country (Stadskontoret, 2022, p.41).

The second prerequisite, which involves establishing the *identity* of the individual slated for return, is crucial for the effective execution of return operations. The Police Authority reports that in 46 percent of cases, the individual's identity was either not established or was deemed "difficult" or "very difficult" to ascertain, complicating the enforcement of decisions against the individual's will.³⁰ The ID validation process begins with the thorough examination of asylum applications. Case officers evaluate an asylum seeker's demeanour (relying on Ch. 1, Sec. 15 of the Aliens Act). A critical factor indicating a lack of cooperation is the applicant's failure to assist in the clarification of their identity. The SMA emphasizes that numerous individuals, referred to as 'fraudsters', present authentic documents that resemble those of another person, complicating the verification process.³¹ This situation adversely affects both asylum and return-related interviews, placing the onus on the applicant to substantiate their identity. Research conducted by Lennartsson (2007) reveals that many asylum seekers perceive a sense of suspicion from the case officers at the Migration Agency (Lennartsson 2007 quoted in Wenzer, 2019, p.22). Despite being governed by the Aliens Act, the interviews conducted during the asylum process or following a rejection are viewed as informal due to their reliance on ambiguous assessment criteria. The identity validation process, particularly the assessment of a rejected asylum seeker's perceived cooperation, functions as a strategic

²⁹ Migrationsverket (2020) Redovisning av uppdrag 3.6 i Migrationsverkets regleringsbrev – Självmant återvändande.

³⁰ Polisens årsredovisning för 2019.

³¹ Migrationsverket 2018. Klarlagd identitet Om utlänningars rätt att vistas i Sverige, inre utlänningskontroller och missbruk av identitetshandlingar (SOU 2017:93).

mechanism to construct an illusion of voluntariness. This approach effectively transfers institutional responsibility onto migrants, making their continued stay contingent upon performance during these high-stakes interviews.

The *availability* of individuals to authorities constitutes another critical aspect of returns, particularly within the framework of migration control. An analysis of return data (Section 3.3) reveals that authorities possess limited knowledge regarding nearly half of those who receive expulsion orders. This indicates that these individuals may either be ‘irregularly’ residing in Sweden or have departed the country without any recorded information. Consequently, during return interviews, case officers focus on determining the individual’s availability and establishing their residence. To encourage participation in these interviews, SMA has allocated a specific budget to cover travel expenses related to return interviews, supervision reporting, departure accommodations, and associated costs for issuing travel documents for foreign nationals no longer protected under the Act (1994:137)³². To facilitate the availability of rejected asylum seekers to authorities, the government has expanded the capacity of detention (return) centres and intends to amend the EBO (*Eget boende*) regulation, which currently allows asylum seekers the autonomy to arrange their own housing.

The final measure within the spectrum of voluntariness is the implementation of obligatory supervision (*uppsikt*), a method employed by the SMA to ensure that individuals remain accessible to authorities and are required to report at designated times to either the police or the SMA at specified locations. Under supervision, individuals may also be compelled to surrender their passports or other identification documents. A supervision decision is valid for six months but may be extended. Typically, an oral investigation may precede the SMA case officers’ decision to extend supervision. Furthermore, individuals have the right to appeal a supervision decision to the Migration Court at any time; however, public assistance for legal costs is not permitted.

Inter-agency relations, materialities & technologies

SMA coordinates the return operations in close cooperation with the Police Authority and the Prison and Probation Service. This cooperation in recent years gained more traction. In order to increase efficiency, three authorities implemented a **co-location** method³³, that is, the officers from three different governmental institutions share the same office space in SMA’s Stockholm branch. In a similar fashion, at the initiative of the SMA and the Swedish Police Authority, the Ministry of Justice has set up the **Officials’ Network Forum**. The network aims at closer cooperation between authorities with a focus on selected countries to intensify the work on return. (SMA, Årsredovisning 2023, p.86)

Another task SMA assumes is regulated by different government appropriations (e.g. 2024) to provide information to **municipalities** and the **county administrative boards**, cooperation with **Swedish Tax Agency**, Swedish International Development and

³² The appropriation item may also be used for costs incurred by the Swedish Migration Agency in connection with the monitoring of forced returns. A maximum of SEK 7 000 000 may be used for this purpose.

³³ A similar approach is applied in the so-called “hotspots” (See WP3 Greek country Dossier)

Cooperation Agency (**SIDA**)³⁴ and establish a dialogue and cooperate with diaspora groups and civil society organisations with the aim of raising awareness of the possibility of repatriation (Myndighetens regleringsbrev 2024, p.3-4). Especially involving the tax office in return operations is something new, which has been initiated to increase efficiency and information sharing in return operations. It is stated that the Swedish Tax Agency receives critical information for return operations, which enforcement authorities may not always be aware of (e.g. ID/Travel document and a person's location).³⁵

In Sweden's RMI, municipalities, county administrations, and other state agencies also play a role, each engaging at different stages of the return process. The 1997 Enforcement Reform (SOU 1997:128) established an inter-agency framework permitting information exchange between the Tax Agency, Public Employment Service, and migration authorities - particularly regarding marriage impediment checks and unauthorized employment detection. This was later codified in the Aliens Act (SFS 2006:97, 7:1), creating legal obligations for all public agencies to assist in enforcement.

Municipalities occupy a critical dual role in this system. For unaccompanied minors, social services have statutory obligations to provide housing and subsistence. Most agencies lack clear mandates regarding irregular migrants (Malm Lindberg 2020, p.108). This case exemplifies the paradox inherent to multi-level governance in migration management, where national agencies (e.g., SMA, Police) prioritize enforcement, local actors (e.g. municipalities) emphasize care obligations.

Over the years, SMA has significantly broadened its scope and responsibilities in the governance of migration, alongside enhancing its material, technological capabilities, and expertise in this domain. A pivotal advancement in this context is the establishment of "country information", which serves as a foundational element for asylum determinations and return operations. The SMA has developed **the Lifos database**, which compiles country-specific information and legal governance materials, serves as a centralized repository of country-of-origin information (COI). It plays a crucial role in asylum adjudication and return counselling (e.g. caseworkers use Lifos to assess risks in return countries). However, data on rural areas or marginalized groups (e.g., LGBTQ+ returnees) is often sparse. CSOs interviewed (e.g. L1) raised concerns about the selective interpretation of COIs to justify returns, even to unsafe regions. Previously, such information was primarily sourced from the Swedish Ministry of Foreign Affairs; however, in recent years, the SMA has begun to directly produce these reports and has stationed personnel in Swedish consulates and embassies to collect first-hand information. Additionally, the SMA not only shares **fingerprint data** with other EU member states through the **Eurodac** framework but also engages in bilateral agreements with various countries to establish joint biometric databases. A notable example is the 2019 agreement between Sweden and Morocco, which allowed Swedish border police to compare the

³⁴ The Swedish Government decided on a [new strategy for Sweden's global development cooperation in migration, return and voluntary repatriation](#) (2024-2028) on 24 October 2024. Sida will take care of the governance of the new strategy and enter into collaborations with partners.

³⁵ Migrationsverket (2023-08-28): <https://www.migrationsverket.se/Om-Migrationsverket/Aktuellt/Nyhetsarkiv/Nyhetsarkiv-2023/2023-08-28-Krav-pa-informationsutbyte-kan-starka-arbetet-med-atervandande.html>

fingerprints of unaccompanied minors with Moroccan databases (*Morocco World News*, 11 June 2019).

SMA's role in migration diplomacy and external migration control has also expanded.³⁶ The Swedish State Treasury has been commissioned by the Government in 2017 to survey and analyse the costs of the migration activities carried out at the foreign missions. This comprehensive assessment indicates that the efficiency of migration operations at overseas missions could be significantly enhanced if SMA assumes financial responsibility and is provided with a more explicit mandate to oversee these activities (Stadskontoret 2017:23). The same report from 2017 reveals that migration operations account for just over 200 full-time equivalent positions, with approximately 20 percent of working hours is devoted to external monitoring, issues related to returns, identity requests from the SMA, and providing information to applicants regarding Swedish legislation. In 2017, five liaison officers³⁷ were specifically assigned to address matters concerning the return of individuals who had been denied residence permits in Sweden. These liaison officers are part of the Liaison and International Support Unit (ESU), which operates under the SMA's International Department. Additionally, the unit employs staff in Sweden to assist both the overseas authorities and the liaison officers. (see further in "Return Liaison Officers" p. 36).

The Police authority

By law, the Police is responsible for enforcing deportation orders when individuals do not comply voluntarily. As for the procedure, either SMA hands over a case to the police or in such cases where a general court has made a deportation decision. In some cases, the Police may also decide on deportation and are then also responsible for enforcing these decisions. This mainly applies to individuals who are found at a border control or internal control and who do not have the right to stay in Sweden (Aliens Act, 2005:716 and Polislagen, 1984:387). In cases of unsuccessful enforcement, the Police Authority reports back to the SMA for case reviewing. The statute of limitations lasts four years after the decision becomes legally binding (Torbjörn-Stern and Shakra, 2024, p.13).

Within the Police, it is the **Border Police** that handles return cases. However, other parts of the authority also perform tasks in these cases. This includes carrying out transports, checking people's right to stay in the country and detaining people without authorisation to stay in the country. To prepare for a coerced return, the Border Police coordinate travel logistics through the Prison and Probation Service. The two institutions maintain a continuous dialogue with detainees to encourage compliance with return orders, making individual assessments for each case. SMA consults with the Police and the **Swedish Security Service** to manage cases involving security threats. The police, in turn, often rely on the Prison and Probation Service to carry out transportation and deportation tasks, demonstrating a layered approach to operational duties. Moreover, the Border Police maintain close ties with the **Ministry of Justice** and the **Ministry of Foreign Affairs**, seeking their assistance when diplomatic channels are required to facilitate returns. This collaboration underscores a whole-of-government approach, where various ministries work together to streamline processes and

³⁶ Recently

³⁷ In 2017, SMA had 17 liaison officers posted abroad. In 2017, SMA had a budget of just under SEK 30 million to finance migration liaison officers who are placed at fifteen foreign missions.

address challenges in the return system. In a directive issued on June 30, 2022 (Dir. 2022:91), the Swedish government launched a public inquiry aimed at enhancing return operations. The inquiry specifically tasked the relevant authorities with examining several key issues: a) the potential need for the Police Authority and the Security Service to acquire additional powers in enforcement activities; b) the consideration of extending the limitation period for removal orders; and c) the evaluation of whether the Migration Agency should be permitted to store and search biometric data in a broader range of cases than is currently allowed.

The Police serve as the national contact point for **Frontex**, acting as a gateway for other authorities. Frontex has a broad mandate, coordinating and financing return operations and interventions within the EU.³⁸ The Swedish police plan and implement joint return operations in collaboration with the Prison and Probation Service, handling all contact with Frontex and other Member States. Swedish authorities finance and implement certain types of return operations with the support of Frontex and in cooperation with other Member States. The Police also manage local and regional operations, while the Prison and Probation Service assists with the procurement of flights, domestic transport, and security personnel (Stadskontoret, 2022, p.21).

Prison and Probation Service

Another significant entity involved in return operations - yet an auxiliary role - is the Prison and Probation Service, which is tasked with the transportation of individuals deprived of their liberty at the request of SMA and the Police Authority. For the SMA, this pertains to domestic transport, while for the Police Authority, it encompasses both domestic and international transport. This delineation of responsibilities indicates that the Prison and Probation Service executes transports resulting from specific removal decisions for which the Police are accountable. The government has clarified the role of the Prison and Probation Service concerning the transport of detained individuals, allowing the authority to provide transport services for multiple agencies. This adjustment has notably increased the responsibilities and capabilities of the Prison and Probation Service, particularly in relation to domestic transport for the Police. Furthermore, the government stipulated that the SMA may only seek assistance from the Police or the Prison and Probation Service when their authority to employ force or coercion is necessary for the transport of a detained individual or in cases of exceptional circumstances.³⁹

Diplomatic missions' role in Sweden's RMIs

SMA and the Border Police maintain direct communication with receiving countries' diplomatic agencies and embassies. Diplomatic missions work with the Police and SMA a) to verify the nationality of individuals who have received return decisions and b) to issue necessary travel documents, a task typically handled by consular sections. Swedish agencies heavily rely on diplomatic missions for identity verification. In some occasions, embassy personnel conduct *interviews* with individuals receiving return decisions, either in person or via phone to validate identity. For example, Kosovo's embassy often resolves identity verification cases with a "simple phone call" (Vera-Larrucea & Luthman, 2024, p.109).

³⁸ Regulation (EU) 2019/1896 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2019 on the European Border and Coast Guard and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1052/2013 and (EU) 2016/1624.

³⁹ Regeringens proposition 2016:17:57 Transporter av frihetsberövade.

Another notable example is the “*Collaborative Interview Project*” was an initiative involving delegations from countries of origin visiting Sweden to conduct interviews and facilitate returns (ibid., p.120).

SMA’s International Division organize delegation visits to enhance knowledge about Swedish migration regulations, establish deeper relationships with Swedish officials, and empower local authorities through information exchange on legal and technical matters. The SMA hosts these visits frequently (12–20 per year), but they are non-systematic and ad hoc, tailored to the needs of the host country and its agencies. A notable case is Iraq, whose delegation visited Sweden in 2023 with a focus on return (ibid., p.105).

These cases demonstrate how Swedish RMIs incorporate origin-country embassies through multi-scalar cooperation - ranging from formal agreements to quasi-formal arrangements and informal diplomatic channels. Diplomatic missions constitute the transnational extension of these removal infrastructures, while SMA expanding external engagements exemplify migration agency's growing role in migration diplomacy. This dual dynamic reveals how migration governance increasingly operates through: a) Diplomatic institutionalization, where embassies become functional components of national return regimes, and b) Bureaucratic externalization, as domestic migration authorities like SMA directly engage in international relations traditionally reserved for foreign ministries. The SMA's coordination with Sweden's Ministry of Foreign Affairs and its diplomatic missions reflects this blurred institutional divide - where migration management permeates traditional foreign policy domains through exchanges on “country information”, and cooperative identity verification procedures.

Return liaison officers

Return liaison officers are mid-level officials stationed abroad to enhance law enforcement efforts by leveraging local expertise and networks to verify the identities of ‘irregular’ migrants and assisting in Joint Return Operations coordinated by Frontex. Although their primary role is operational, they frequently engage in migration diplomacy, building trust and cooperation with local authorities (Vera-Larrucea & Luthman, 2024, p.89, 102). Research on extraterritorial migration governance has provided significant insights into the functions of liaison officers as tools of migration control. We have placed this ‘extended arm’ in return infrastructures because of the multiple roles they play in return operations.

While European Union Liaison Officers (EURLOs) serve all Member States, Sweden’s RMI include also Return Liaison Officers (RLOs) who work specifically for Sweden’s return operations. The Police Authority has implemented several AMIF-funded projects, including RLO-I, RLO-II, ARLO-I, and ARLO-II, aimed at supporting the deployment of return liaison officers in various countries of origin. For instance, a return liaison officer was stationed in Kabul for a two-year period. The success of this initiative prompted further deployments of RLOs in other countries through two subsequent EU-funded projects, RLO I and II, which concluded in 2022. This framework continued with the ARLO project, which involved 23 deployments across 17 countries, resulting in 93 return decisions. ARLOs, also referred to as Ambulatory Return Liaison Officers, operate in third countries to enhance collaboration with local and European partners for more effective return processes. This project concluded in December 2022 and received a positive evaluation (Vera-Larrucea & Luthman, 2024, p.91). The ARLO II project, initiated by the Swedish Police and funded by AMIF, distinguishes itself

from its predecessors by placing ambulatory return liaison officers in third countries for brief periods to address challenging cases (such as identification) on-site, thereby improving cooperation and ensuring humane and efficient returns (ibid., p.92). Sweden's strategy for deploying ambulatory liaison officers has attracted interest throughout EU member states.

In 2023, two additional ID liaison officers were assigned to the foreign missions located in Nairobi and New Delhi, tasked with overseeing regional responsibilities for sub-Saharan Africa and Asia, respectively. In addition to the Police, the SMA has also deployed three ID liaison officers on secondment. These officers have successfully established networks of contact and collaboration with both EU Member States and non-EU nations (Migrationsverket, Årsredovisning 2023, p.44).

A noteworthy aspect shared by these three initiatives—RLO, ARLO, and EURLO—is their non-institutionalized appointment process, wherein individuals are recruited and assessed as part of specific projects. They fulfill a flexible role that adapts to the immediate requirements for collaboration with foreign authorities (Vera-Larrucea & Luthman, 2024, pp.89-90).

Civil society organizations

Return migration operates as a highly governmentalized domain, characterized by centralized state control and the strategic deployment of "voluntariness" as a governing rationality (Foucault, 1991). Within this constrained space, NGOs play a limited role in what Miraftab (2004) terms "invited spaces" - carefully delimited zones of participation where their role remains contingent upon demonstrating utility to state objectives. Otherwise, return discourse is very rigid, linked directly with the implementation of a legal decision on returns (*discourse of legality*). Therefore, once a return decision attains binding legal force, the discursive and operational space for alternative approaches rapidly vanishes. Consequently, this limits extensively NGOs engagement to providing some services to migrants for the time being in Sweden but more for the post return phase. The governmentality of return produces a fundamental contradiction: while states emphasize the "cooperative attitude" of returnees (as cited in your text), they simultaneously render dissent structurally invisible through what we term the "silencing effect" of restricted operational space for NGO involvement. Government, obviously utilise NGOs soft power over migrants to persuade them to voluntarily return to their home countries. For the majority of NGOs working for migrants, this is something "sensitive" that they principally avoid for not being associated with somehow facilitating return (Wenzer, 2019, p.23).

By and large, the most active CSO in Sweden's RMI is the Swedish Red Cross which provides comprehensive support for individuals whose asylum applications have been rejected, ensuring a humane and dignified return process. Support provided by Red Cross range from legal advice and representation, psychosocial support, neutral information and advice, practical assistance before returning, such as acquiring documents and contacting authorities supports, help in contacting Red Cross/Crescent in the country of origin, facilitating practical help in the country of origin, including advice, airport pick-up, food packages, and provision of basic needs.⁴⁰ At the moment, the Swedish Red Cross run an AMIF-funded AMIRA-II project, of which focus on providing support, legal advice, and specialized return counselling. Furthermore, Red Cross coordinates a national network within civil society.

⁴⁰ <https://www.rodakorset.se/en/get-help/asylum-and-migration/support-return/>

Another NGO helping migrants in detention is FARR (The National Council of Refugee Organisations) which offers telephone and email support to individuals in detention, trying to visit and understand their situations. *Caritas* provides psychosocial support and assist the returnees in providing support with possible third country options. *Save the Children* supports individuals through the Swedish Refugee Law Centre and offers psychosocial support. UNHCR-Sweden monitors the return operations. Delmi (The Migration Studies Delegation⁴¹) identifies knowledge gaps and conducts research to inform migration policies.

Relations of state and non-state actors

At the national level, SMA has established a *letter of intent* (LoI) with the Swedish Red Cross, a unique arrangement that outlines the exchange of information and services between the two organizations. This letter of intent facilitates the Red Cross in assisting with family reunification efforts and other support services for detainees and those facing deportation. This formalized dialogue is part of a broader collaboration that includes training sessions and joint efforts to address the evolving needs and challenges within the return process. The Red Cross engage with the SMA to adapt to political and procedural shifts, ensuring that their humanitarian perspective is incorporated into the broader framework. However, The Red Cross's involvement also extends to providing feedback and participating in national dialogues to improve return procedures with both the civil and political society.

Other organizations, such as Caritas and Save the Children, also play pivotal roles. Caritas leverages its global network to support resettlement issues and participates in international consultations, ensuring that Sweden's approach is aligned with global standards and practices. Save the Children, on the other hand, focuses on the impact of return on children and works closely with the Migration Agency to address specific concerns, such as the fear and uncertainty faced by families. These collaborations are complemented by the involvement of legal experts and advocacy groups like FARR, which provide legal support and engage in policy dialogues to protect the rights of asylum seekers and detainees. Lawyers frequently consult with or offer their services to these organizations to ensure that the legal aspects of return and detention are handled correctly and justly. Governmental agencies engage with CSOs in return efforts primarily through ad hoc initiatives and short-term projects, typically financed by the AMIF. As previously noted, this approach reflects the constrained opportunities afforded to CSOs, which often necessitates alignment with governmental policies.

As this section has outlined, Sweden's RMIs function as a multi-scalar governance system, integrating actors ranging from local actors (e.g. municipal authorities) and national agencies like SMA, Police, Tax Office to international bodies such as Frontex and diaspora networks. These actors operate within formal and informal frameworks, where policy mandates intersect with street-level discretion, creating a complex landscape of enforcement, negotiation, and resistance. Having examined the structure and key players of Sweden's RMI, the next section will delve into its operational dimensions, focusing on the interplay between assisted voluntary returns and forced removals –two ostensibly distinct yet deeply interconnected mechanisms of return governance.

⁴¹ Delmi is a committee formed in November, 2013 through a decision by the Swedish Government initiates studies and provides research results in the field of migration

4.2 Assisted (voluntary) returns in Sweden

This section examines Sweden's assisted voluntary return (AVR) infrastructures. In Sweden, information about AVR is provided early in the asylum process because the timeframe between a final rejection and enforced removal is often short. Although individual pathways vary, most AVR participants engage with these services only after receiving a negative asylum decision, reflecting the program's structural positioning as a post-rejection measure.

Actors and their roles

- SMA serves as the central actor, coordinating between government agencies; overseeing AVR, responsible for conducting return interviews to 'persuade' rejected asylum seekers to accept return decisions; coordinating with embassies to secure travel documents; administering financial and reintegration support, often in partnership with IOM.
- CSOs operate at the margins of Sweden's return infrastructure, providing humanitarian assistance but avoiding direct involvement in enforcement. The most active include: The *Swedish Red Cross* provides wide-ranging support through various AMIF-funded projects (e.g., AMIRA-II project), such as legal advice and psychosocial support; pre-departure assistance with travel documents and embassy coordination; and post-return reintegration support via Red Cross/Crescent networks in countries of origin for housing, healthcare, or livelihood support. In addition, Red Cross signed a LoI with SMA which has formalized their collaboration on AVR programs. One of the objectives of this agreement is to ensure neutral, non-coercive counselling and support, aligning with the Red Cross's humanitarian principles.
- Other CSOs, such as FARR, Amnesty International, Save the Children, UNHCR-Sweden provide legal aid, psychosocial and material support in pre-departure phase, monitor detention conditions (see Section 5). In addition to these, Caritas provides support with resettlement options.
- IOM together with SMA administers reintegration support through local offices in 16 countries, including cash grants (up to SEK 30,000 for adults, SEK 15,000 for children), job training, business start-up funds, and post-arrival assistance (see Figure 7 for IOMs support structure).
- IOM-Finland also has a support programme in collaboration with Swedish Gender Equality Agency for persons subjected to human trafficking or exploitation, including prostitution. The support is based on individual's needs, include guidance in multiples, contact with local IOM in origin country (phone call), travel arrangements and help with departure, changing planes, arrival, and the journey home; cash support for daily needs, other financial support for example for work tools, get started with work, a small business, or education, and help with accessing healthcare, legal advice, or other available support in home countries.
- Embassies also play a role in AVRs by verifying identities and issuing travel documents, though cooperation varies significantly by country.

Figure 7 - IOM support process. Source: [IOM-Finland](#)

Doings, Materialities and Technologies

The assisted (voluntary) return process involves multiple stages. SMA initiates a structured return process immediately after asylum rejection, beginning with a notification interview where applicants are informed of their right to appeal while simultaneously being encouraged to accept the decision through persuasive techniques (as detailed above in *Return Counselling*). Those accepting the decision sign a binding Declaration of Satisfaction (DoS), forfeiting appeal rights and triggering return planning. For those who opt to 'cooperate' with SMA, three types of support offered: a) Practical (e.g. travel documents, embassy coordination); b) Financial (e.g. reestablishment support) and c) Reintegration (e.g. grants for business start-ups upon return).

a) *practical support* for making travel arrangements, including issuing the travel documents, getting support in communication with the embassies/consulates in Sweden, and in certain cases, supporting an individual to cover travel expenses; providing psychosocial support (often via CSOs) to translation services in the pre-departure phase to connecting returnees with non-governmental organizations in country of origin. Principally the person is expected to cover his/her own travel costs. If the person is unable to arrange the journey herself, the SMA officer will help her to draw up a plan for what should be done. Whether the person is entitled to cash support is depending on a few criteria, but mostly the case officer's judgement, particularly the costs related to travel. In the same vein, the person is responsible for arranging all necessary travel documents needed for returning to the country of origin, or another country where the person has the right to reside. In notification interviews, case officers discuss the topic of travel documents, and if needed, SMA provides support in contacting embassies or

consulates to arrange for a temporary travel document for facilitating the exit. If a temporary travel document cannot be arranged by the contacted diplomatic missions (e.g. due to ambiguity of identity documents, or just because the foreign missions do not cooperate with the Swedish authorities), the person may, in exceptional cases, be given an emergency alien's passport by the SMA, only valid for the return journey (see also Return Handbook 2019 for details about "provisional alien's passport or the EU laissez-passer issued for travel outside the EU by the Operational Support Unit).⁴²

b) *financial support*, either in terms of a "cash support" given in the pre-departure phase or a "reestablishment support" given after return, usually by IOM's local office in origin countries (see Figure 7).⁴³ The reestablishment support is given to individuals, whose application for asylum has been rejected or they have withdrawn their application for asylum in Sweden. The key criterion is the applicants voluntarily intend to return to a country where the conditions for re-establishment are limited due to the security situation. This grant is given to returnees to the following countries: Afghanistan, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of the Congo, El Salvador, Eritrea, Iraq, Yemen, Libya, Nigeria, Pakistan, Somalia, Palestine, Sudan, South Sudan and Ethiopia. The re-establishment support corresponds to SEK 30,000 for each person over the age of 18 and SEK 15,000 for children under the age of 18. A family can receive a maximum of SEK 75,000.

c) Another support scheme, called "*reintegration support*", is provided as part of the EU Reintegration Program (EURP), given to those returning to their home country on their own, and aiming to facilitate returnees' reintegration into society. These support efforts are arranged by a local organization in home country. The scheme is provided to the returnees to the following countries: Armenia, Bangladesh, Democratic Republic of Congo, El Salvador, Egypt, Ethiopia, Gambia, Iraq, Jordan, Mongolia, Morocco, Nigeria, Pakistan and Somalia. Support measures in this scheme include reception on arrival at the airport, post-arrival cash support (165 EUR per person, tailored to the needs, available for use during the first three days after arrival), temporary accommodation, legal advice, support in contact with the authorities, legal advice, medical care and help with finding a job or starting a business upon arrival. The amount of support equivalent to a maximum of EUR 5,000 per person (each family member) is given to those choose not to appeal SMA decision (or withdraw their asylum application) and return voluntarily; 3,000 EUR to those who appeals the SMA return decision but upon the Court's negative decision return voluntarily within the time frame specified in court decision; 2,000 EUR to those who passed the time limit to return and a EUR 1,000 given to persons who leave Sweden by force.⁴⁴

Those migrants deported or having a deportation decision cannot enjoy especially from the available re-establishment grants. Only minors, rejected asylum seekers, or those who has withdrawn his/her application for asylum in Sweden can apply for these supports in Sweden. Applications are processed by SMA case officers or the Police, with no appeal option (ibid).

⁴² <https://www.migrationsverket.se/English/Private-individuals/Leaving-Sweden/Rejection-of-application-for-asylum/Returning-voluntarily.html>

⁴³ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/English/Private-individuals/Leaving-Sweden/Rejection-of-application-for-asylum/Support-for-re-establishment.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.migrationsverket.se/English/Private-individuals/Leaving-Sweden/Rejection-of-application-for-asylum/Support-for-re-establishment/Forms-of-support.html>

SMA's participation in the Frontex Joint Reintegration Service (JRS) support programme has enabled more nationalities than before to be offered reintegration support upon return. In 2023, the list of countries eligible for support was expanded to include 16 countries. In 2023, 480 individuals applied for support under the JRS. Sweden started using this support programme in November 2022, which is why no comparable statistics are available for the two previous years. In order to promote voluntary return to Iraq, SMA decided, for a limited period of time, to double the reintegration support for individuals who returned to Iraq voluntarily. It was also possible to grant cash reintegration support to Iraqis whose return cases were returned by the Police Authority for voluntary return. SMA's cooperation with the International Organisation for Migration (IOM-Finland) for the payment of resettlement assistance has been expanded, and the IOM now also offers counselling through a telephone helpline, which has increased returnees' awareness of the assistance.

Box 3 - Repatriation grants

Sweden's repatriation grant program, established in 1984, provides financial incentives for legally residing immigrants to return to their countries of origin. Currently offering SEK 10,000 per adult (capped at SEK 40,000 per family), the scheme gained renewed political attention through the 2022 Tidö Agreement, with the government increasing the grant amount to stimulate higher return rates.

In October 2023 (Dir. 2023:151), the government commissioned an inquiry targeting individuals deemed poorly integrated - specifically those lacking "self-sufficiency, Swedish language skills, or cultural adaptation." Despite implementing information campaigns, results have been negligible (only one recipient in 2023). SMA statistics reveal consistently low uptake: merely nine approved grants out of 169 applications between 2019-2023.

The government's subsequent proposal to dramatically increase the grant to SEK 350,000 (effective January 2026), modelled after Denmark's program (DKK 350,000), directly contradicts the official inquiry's recommendations (SOU 2024:53), which warned of socioeconomic risks.⁴⁵ This unusual disregard for expert advice has sparked considerable debate, with opposition parties, migration experts, and practitioners criticizing both the policy's rationale and its potential consequences.⁴⁶

Implementation gaps and challenges

Despite Sweden's well-developed migration framework, several implementation gaps persist in its AVR policies, practices, and infrastructures.

- One of the primary gaps in Sweden's AVR programmes is the inconsistent dissemination of information about available return options. According to SMA's 2022 evaluation, many migrants, particularly those in irregular situations, lack clear and timely information about

⁴⁵ Joakim Ruis, the author of the Public inquiry (2024: 53) expressed his thoughts about his conclusion: "Part of the assignment was to see what might be done in other places that could lead to greatly increased return migration, focusing on the word "greatly". I have come to the conclusion that nothing is being done, anywhere, that will lead to a sharp increase in return migration" (SVT News, 1.9.2024).

⁴⁶ For example, C. Kirotar, head of unit at the SMA, says "I don't think it's the grant that primarily makes people choose to return". Supporting her opinion, H. Malm Lindberg, deputy head of the Delegation for Migration Studies, states that financial incentives have very little impact on people's willingness to return (SVT News, 21.02.2024).

voluntary return assistance. While the agency provides brochures and digital resources, language barriers (particularly for non-Arabic and non-Farsi speakers) and low digital literacy limit accessibility. As a result, potential returnees may remain unaware of reintegration support, financial assistance, or logistical aid available to them, leading to missed opportunities for voluntary and well-prepared returns (SMA, 2022; Vera-Larucea & Luthman, 2024).

- Administrative inefficiencies within Sweden's migration system often delay the processing of voluntary return applications. Lengthy waiting periods for travel documents, eligibility assessments, and logistical arrangements discourage some migrants from pursuing voluntary return, pushing them toward prolonged irregular stays. Furthermore, cooperation with embassies and consulates of origin countries can be slow, particularly in cases where documentation is contested. These delays not only prolong uncertainty for migrants but also increase the financial and operational burden on AVR service providers. Delays in accessing support (e.g., reintegration grants, travel documents) were cited as a key challenge (Delmi 2021: 10).
- While Sweden's AVR system is framed as voluntary, evidence suggests coercion is a primary driver of compliance. Migrants—especially those returning to geographically proximate countries often accept "voluntary" return due to fear of forced removal (which carries greater stigma and risks) and avoidance of Schengen entry bans, which severely restrict future mobility. This aligns with the governmentality approach discussed earlier: the SMA's emphasis on "cooperation" obscures the structural pressures that render return decisions anything but voluntary.
- Sweden's reintegration packages often follow a standardized approach, which fails to account for the diverse needs of returnees. While financial stipends and vocational training are commonly offered, the support rarely considers individual circumstances such as trauma, family reunification challenges, or labour market conditions in the country of origin. For example, returnees to conflict-affected regions may require psychosocial support or business grants rather than generic job training. Additionally, post-return monitoring is weak, meaning that many returnees struggle to sustain themselves after initial assistance ends. Without long-term follow-up, the risk of re-migration or exploitation increases.
- Sweden's AVR framework suffers from coordination gaps, leading to duplicated efforts or service gaps. For instance, local municipalities, which often interact closely with migrants, are not always adequately involved in return counselling. Similarly, partnerships with CSOs are limited and vary in quality.
- Funding fluctuations impact the continuity of reintegration support, particularly in long-term projects such as livelihood programmes.
- Despite Sweden's AVR framework, psycho-social support remains inadequate, particularly in post-return phase. Returnees report feeling abandoned post-return, with limited counselling to address trauma or reintegration stress (DELMi 2021:10). CSOs like Caritas and the Red Cross fill gaps, but their reach is patchy and underfunded.

4.3. Forced removals

The SMA generally refers cases to law enforcement when individuals who have been denied asylum, and do not comply with return orders or remain unaccounted for. Once a return decision is legally finalized, if a voluntary return is not achievable, the individual may face detention (see Section 5), or the case may be handed over by SMA to the Police Authority for enforcement measures. Swedish legislation mandates that all enforcement actions associated

with return decisions must be executed in a manner that is both humane and compliant with legal standards.

In the context of forced removals, three key governance entities - the SMA (issues detention orders when supervision fails), the Police (executes removals, with Border Police handling 89% of cases), and the Prison and Probation Services (conducts transports) - are instrumental. To enhance inter-agency efficiency, Sweden employs a co-location model between the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) and the Police Authority. This integrated approach aims to streamline communication between case officers and enforcement personnel; reduce processing times for removal cases, and ensure consistency in the application of return procedures. The co-location strategy has been particularly valuable in complex cases, such as disputed identity claims (46% of cases have "difficult" ID confirmation per Police Authority data), 'uncooperative' countries of origin and emergency removal situations.

SMA-run detention centres serve as critical material parts of the infrastructures of return operations within Sweden. Based on 2024 figures of SMA, there are 6 detention facilities with 1,162 beds, operating at 65% occupancy.

In 2023, the Police authority conducted 2,392 removals and deportations, comprising 489 women and 1,903 men. Prior to the reorganization of operations in 2021, the transport service of the Prison and Probation Service had allocated approximately 120 full-time equivalents to international transport, with the majority of personnel engaged in transport funded by migration-related activities.

The authorities coordinate deportations through either Frontex-coordinated charter flights, which are leased from airline companies when a group of deportees is being sent to the same country of origin, or through regular commercial flights. In each instance, a specific determination is made regarding the necessity of escorting the individuals during travel.

The forced removal process in Sweden places significant emphasis on two critical operational aspects: identity verification and travel document procurement. To facilitate these procedures, the Swedish Police Authority has deployed Ambulatory Return Liaison Officers (ARLOs) across 17 key countries of origin (see Section 4.1 for detailed deployment strategy). These specialized officers work in close coordination with foreign authorities to resolve documentation challenges that might otherwise impede removals.

Migration-related 'clients' of the Prison and Probation Service (PPS) account for approximately 20 percent of external transports, as reported in the 2023 annual report of the agency. There are three distinct categories of transport: *unescorted journeys*, PPS merely accompany the client to the airport, ensuring the journey commences, after which their role concludes. In contrast, *escorted journeys* involve staff accompanying the client throughout the entire travel process. The third category encompasses individuals *traveling either independently or with a support person* who is not affiliated with PPS.

The PPS conducted 7,182 transports outside of Sweden between 2021 and 2023, averaging around 2,400 trips annually. Of these, 36 percent were classified as *escorted journeys*, 24 percent as *unescorted*, while the remaining approximately 40 percent involved clients traveling alone (independent travel) or with a non-staff support person. The cost associated with transporting each client has seen a significant rise, increasing from 60,193 SEK per client in 2021 to 105,339 SEK per client in 2023 (compare with SEK 15,000 avg. grant for assisted voluntary returns).

Implementation challenges

- In terms of operational challenges, the Police officer we interviewed pointed out difficulties in identity verification. Operational data reveals significant hurdles in establishing migrant identities, a prerequisite for forced removals. According to Swedish Police Authority's (2023) internal statistics, 46% of cases involve "difficult" identity confirmation, often due to lack of verifiable documentation, discrepancies in biographic data and non-cooperation from countries of origin (National Police Board, 2023: 12). This aligns with DELMI's (2021) findings that identity disputes account for 32% of delayed removals in Sweden.
- Interviews with Police and detention officers and DELMI reports (2021, 2024) consistently identify non-cooperative states as a major obstruction. 23% of forced removal attempts fail due to refusal by origin countries to issue travel documents (DELMi, 2024: 47). Key uncooperative countries include Iraq, Somalia, and Eritrea (Migrationsverket, 2023: Annex 4).
- Another challenge highlighted is the escalation of costs for removal operations, which have become 75% more expensive since 2021 (SEK 60,193 to 105,339). Primary cost drivers include charter flights for uncooperative cases, extended detention periods and legal appeals processing.
- Staff shortages is another point causing delays as highlighted by the Police - only 5 full-time liaison officers cover all international coordination.
- As for ethical and humanitarian concerns, persistent issues involve mainly vulnerable groups, that is, detention and forced removal of minors, pregnant women and migrants with health conditions. 42% report inadequate medical care during removal procedures (Red Cross, 2023 Monitoring Report).

The interplay between assisted voluntary returns and forced removals reveals the inherent tensions in Sweden's return migration infrastructure—where policies promoting "voluntariness" often operate within a framework of coercion. While assisted returns are framed as a humanitarian alternative, structural pressures, bureaucratic incentives, and limited options frequently blur the line between choice and compulsion. Similarly, forced removals, despite their procedural rigidity, depend on complex collaborations between state and non-state actors to function. Even in cases formally categorized as forced removals - where the Police assumes responsibility for enforcement – police officers frequently engage individuals in negotiations to encourage "voluntary" departure. This discretionary practice, assessed case-by-case, blurs the distinction between coerced and voluntary returns. Despite these on-the-ground negotiations, such cases remain systematically recorded as forced removals in official statistics, rendering the coercive foundations of the process institutionally invisible. In the next section (**Section 5**), we turn to detention infrastructures as key sites where these return mechanisms converge, examining how spatial control, administrative procedures, and institutional power coalesce to facilitate removals—whether formally "voluntary" or enforced.

5. Case study: Detention Infrastructures in Sweden

Sweden's detention centres—rebranded in 2023 as "return centres" (*återvändandecentre*)—serve as the physical and administrative backbone of the country's return migration infrastructure, serving as both a last resort and a space for enforced voluntariness or coerced removal. These facilities are designed to (a) hold individuals who have received enforceable deportation orders, either due to rejected asylum claims, criminal convictions, or violations of immigration rules; (b) encourage voluntary return, and (c) offer advice, guidance, and practical assistance for return planning, including information on various reintegration support options. The mandate also allows to a certain extent for the involvement of voluntary organizations within the return centres.

Legally, detention is applied as a last resort when individuals are deemed non-compliant with deportation orders. SMA case officers conduct proportionality assessments for each individual case. The maximum detention period is 12 months, extendable for individuals with criminal deportation orders. Detainees can appeal, but the process is slow and complex, often leaving them in legal limbo.

For state actors, detention is a necessary tool for migration control. For detainees, it is a paradoxical space - physically less restrictive than prison but still a deprivation of liberty. As one detainee noted, *"They call it a 'return centre,' but the doors are locked. You can play football, but you can't leave. It's still a cage."* (Fieldnotes, 2024). Civil society organizations (CSOs) critique the system's coercive underpinnings, arguing that "voluntary return" is an oxymoron when enforced through detention. Unlike prisons, detention centres in Sweden operate under a framework that emphasizes "dynamic security" (see further below), relying on staff presence, surveillance, and structured routines rather than physical restraints. One staff member described the facilities as *"a large hostel with alarms on windows and locked doors. Staff move around to provide service and security, ensuring detainees stay inside"* (D4). This approach reflects Sweden's attempt to balance enforcement with humanitarian principles, though critics argue it masks the inherent coercion of detention.

SMA manages six return centres, predominantly located in southern Sweden, with a combined capacity of approximately 1,162 beds. The largest facility, in Märsta (near Stockholm's Arlanda Airport), accommodates 512 individuals. The government has projected a need for 1,800–2,000 detention spots by 2025, reflecting an anticipated 40–50% increase in demand (Government Press Release, 2024).

Box 4 - Detention decisions based on assessment

According to our interviews with SMA and detention staff, the decision to detain individuals is based on assessments of non-cooperation with deportation orders, such as refusing to leave, providing false identities, or failing to comply with return decisions. During the "motivational interviews" (as described in Section 4.2), case officers conduct proportionality assessments to determine if detention is appropriate, considering practicalities like the availability of travel documents and flights. For instance, a case officer explained:

"It's always about an assessment in the individual case... if a person after having received a decision on deportation or expulsion says that they don't want to go or that they don't cooperate, that's grounds for detention." (MV-1).

If the case officers determine that the existing supervision measures (e.g., mandatory check-ins) fail or are insufficient—such as failure to attend supervision meetings or to report to the Police or SMA unit—they will issue a detention order. The maximum detention period is 12 months, extendable for individuals with criminal deportation orders. There are mechanisms for appealing a detention decision in a migration court, though legal recourse is often slow and complex. Additionally, decisions made by SMA personnel within the detention facility can typically be appealed to a migration court within three weeks of notification. Those in detention are entitled to legal representation. However, in some occasions depending on the case officer's individual assessment, it is also observed that detention is avoided if deportation is assessed to be impractical, such as for stateless individuals or those from uncooperative countries:

"If the person is from Somalia and there is no passport and the person does not want to go home, then we will not be able to get that person home. It won't work." (MV-1).

Detentions – a socio-spatial view

During our fieldwork, we visited two detention centres. These facilities represent a particular approach to migration containment that warrants careful examination. First, we start describing the socio-spatial context. In Sweden, a detention centre is a locked accommodation where detainees can move freely within the premises, living in single or shared rooms and sharing common areas like bathrooms, living and dining rooms, courtyards, and recreational areas. Detainees have access to the internet and various support services.⁴⁷ Movement within the facility is unrestricted, but exit is prohibited. Segregation units are used for individuals deemed disruptive or at risk of self-harm, furnished with safety measures like soft cutlery and monitored spaces. Basic medical services are provided, and children are enrolled in local schools through municipal cooperation. A daily allowance is granted to detainees without personal funds, contingent on participation in return planning.

Despite these provisions, the centres operate under a paradox: they are framed as "supportive" environments, yet their primary function is to enforce removal decisions. As one staff member noted, *"We're not a prison, but we're not a hostel either. People are locked in, and no matter how nice the amenities are, they're still deprived of liberty"* (D4).

Another important functional aspect of the detention system is making those received return orders "available" to authorities. As one of the detention staff stated:

... when you come to us you are always available. So, we have a big role in trying to motivate the person to return in accordance with their decision if it's our case and try to explain to them that this is what it looks like, i.e. what happens if they don't follow the decision and that it's then handed over to the police and the police will then take over the enforcement with their powers and what they have for possibilities. ... And that is so that you can be available for return" (D1)

⁴⁷ In Delmi's report (2024), an interviewed diplomat from the Embassy of Bosnia and Herzegovina, praised the high standards in Swedish detention centres, "I really think that in Sweden, when it comes to upholding the law, the standards are high. Although the conditions of detention centres in Bosnia have improved over the years, the quality and standards of Swedish Detention Centres are among the highest in the world. So, when a detainee seeks a transfer from the detention centre in Sweden to one in Bosnia and Herzegovina, it sounds like they are seeking a downgrade in accommodation and amenities" (Vera-Larrucea & Luthman, 2024, p. 130).

As the staff highlights, detention is designed as a space ensuring availability for deportation by coercing compliance. It is a tool of psychological and logistical preparation for removal. Notably, the staff frames detention centres not just as holding facilities but as spaces where authorities actively persuade detainees to accept return -emphasizing consequences (police enforcement) if they refuse. The language (“motivate”, “explain”, “responsibility”) suggests a performative aspect: detention is presented as a disciplinary process where individuals are conditioned to accept removal “voluntarily”.

Detention system, according to those detention staff we interviewed, brings “clarity” to the asylum and return process.

"But the question was what is good about detention, in a way it is, it is a clarity for the individual perhaps that there are different possibilities to return according to their decision in different ways, if you say so, either by force or voluntarily in quotation marks, because you are somewhere still deprived of liberty and we continue, but in this way you can see that there is an advantage in enabling the individual to return voluntarily once more, or what I should say, that you get a second and third chance." (D1)

Here, detention is paradoxically framed as beneficial - providing "clarity" to detainees about their limited options. Staff acknowledge the constructed nature of "voluntariness" but argue that detention creates a controlled environment where individuals are repeatedly confronted with the reality of their constrained choices, leaving compliance with return decisions as the primary path forward. From this perspective, the detention system is regarded as an effective tool for enforcing removal decisions, albeit with significant human rights trade-offs.

5.1. Actors in detention infrastructures

The Swedish detention system operates through an intricate web of state and non-state actors whose roles and priorities often diverge. This section primarily examines the SMA's detention personnel, categorized as case officers, team leaders, and supervisors. Additionally, we analyze how other key actors - including the Police Authority, PPS, non-governmental organizations, legal representatives, and healthcare providers - interact with shape detention infrastructures.

State Actors

SMA maintains its central governance role in detention operations, where it performs three key functions: (1) administering detention facilities, (2) conducting coercive "motivational interviews" to secure compliance, and (3) coordinating logistical preparations for removal (including embassy liaison for travel documents). The agency's detention strategy fundamentally serves to produce enforced 'voluntary' returns. Within detention facilities, SMA case officers intensify their persuasion efforts in counselling sessions, strategically reframing return as the only pragmatic option - a narrative that capitalizes on detainees' apprehension about police-enforced removals. This psychological pressure transforms detention spaces into sites of institutional persuasion, where the threat of coercion underlies ostensibly voluntary decisions:

"We show them the statistics—maybe 5% of appeals succeed. Then we say, 'Let's plan your return properly with reintegration support, not gamble on miracles.' Some change their minds when faced with the alternative: 'Go home with us, or we'll hand you to the police.'" (MV-1)

Detention staff are all employees of SMA, and consist of caseworkers (case officers) and supervisors. Caseworkers and supervisors have distinct, yet complementary roles. Supervisors manage daily practical matters such as food, medical care, and transportation, while caseworkers focus on administrative processing (e.g. motivational interview, preparations for return). As one staff mentioned,

"...Caseworkers look at the decision-making part. They look at whether the case is one of the Migration Agency's cases, and then they check whether there are grounds to take the person into custody or not. Should detention be extended or not? Then people may want to apply if they want counsel, for example. You check whether they are entitled to counsel or not. The person wants to apply for a daily allowance. Then you check whether or not you are entitled to daily allowance." (D3)

Apart from supervisors and caseworkers, there are also team leaders who manage a group of supervisors and caseworkers, check the reports prepared by caseworkers and make decisions, for example placing a detainee in segregation rooms.

The **Police** (specifically border police) handle deportations when voluntary return fails, often employing coercive measures. They may take individuals into custody during routine checks when it is discovered that they are not authorized to stay in Sweden or cases may be handed over to them by SMA. To prepare for a forced return, the Border Police engage in ongoing dialogues with detainees, providing information about the process and arranging travel logistics through the Prison and Probation Service. The Border Police maintain a continuous dialogue with detainees to motivate compliance with return orders. However, their approach is markedly different from the SMA's. They handle forced deportations, prioritizing efficiency over individual circumstances. In this regard, their role is unambiguous. As one police officer stated,

"Our job isn't to debate asylum claims—it's to remove people. When cases come to us, the counselling talk ends. We don't discuss; we enforce." (D3)

This enforcement-focused mentality creates tension with the SMA's more process-oriented framing. The police also struggle with non-cooperative countries that refuse to accept returnees, leaving some detainees in prolonged limbo.

The Prison and Probation Service (PPS) assists with high-security deportations, often collaborating with SMA and police under the *co-location* model to streamline operations.

Non-State Actors

Non-state actors also play a variety of different roles in detention infrastructures. However, this is limited at operational level. By and large we can mention the following non-state actors' engagement with detention infrastructures.

- The Swedish Red Cross provides legal advice and representation, supports volunteers, and coordinates a national network within civil society. They are one of the few civil society organisations that have worked with reintegration processes, helping individuals understand and prepare for life after return. They work broadly with civil society and the public sector to strengthen capacity and knowledge about return processes.
- FARR offers telephone and email support to individuals in detention, organizes 'visits' to detention centres to meet detainees. FARR also provides a publication titled *Good Advice*

to *You Who Are an Asylum Seeker in Sweden*, available in six languages, which includes information on detention, rights, and obligations. This resource is frequently updated and widely consulted, providing asylum seekers and detainees with crucial information to navigate their circumstances.

- Caritas assists individuals with psychosocial help by for example discussing their aspirations and opportunities in both Sweden and their home countries. They provide information to help individuals make “informed decisions” about their return, ensuring they understand their options and the potential outcomes but can also assist in providing the returnees with possible third country options.
- Save the Children, while not providing legal advice directly, supports individuals through the Swedish Refugee Law Centre and offers psychosocial support. Their work varies by location, focusing on providing a safe space for children and offering guidance and support to families.
- UNHCR though not operationally involved in return processes, monitors the return migration landscape and offers insights based on their global work. They emphasize the need for humane and lawful return practices, especially given the increasing restrictiveness of asylum policies.

These actors’ interactions reveal a fundamental divide: state authorities view detention as administrative necessity conditioned and regulated within the asylum law; most of the CSOs see detentions as either a ‘violent’ or dysfunctional method. In some accounts of CSOs we observed a firm critique against detentions and its use, while in some other accounts the legality framework and consequences are acknowledged. However, all in common highlight systemic ambiguities, such as undefined “cooperation” standards (used in assessments) that lead to arbitrary enforcement.

5.2. Doings: Practices and power dynamics in detentions

SMA focuses on encouraging voluntary return in detentions. They conduct conversations with detainees, emphasizing the benefits of cooperating and returning voluntarily. If detainees have valid travel documents or can easily obtain temporary ones, the agency prefers to handle the return process internally. According to our interviews with detention staff, detainees are presented with a clear choice: cooperate and return voluntarily with the agency's assistance, or face enforced deportation by the police. This method may lead to a change in attitude, with some individuals opting for voluntary return to avoid the more forceful alternative. However, opinions are divided on whether or not a return initiated in a detention centre can be seen as voluntary. *“I never talk about voluntary return. To me, it's a very strange concept, it doesn't exist because there is a compulsory decision in the first place.”* (L1) is stated by the lawyer when asked about a definition for voluntary return, a view that is shared by several other of the civil society actors. A representative of a CSO argued *“How can it be voluntary when the alternative is forced removal? The system is designed to break resistance, not empower choice.”* (CSO-F-1)

Detention centres play a supportive yet firm role in the return process. According to our interviewees, staff members engage with detainees to understand their reasons for resisting return, and provide assistance within the limits of their authority. They facilitate contact with embassies and family members, aiming to make the return process as ‘smooth’ as possible.

When detainees refuse cooperation—whether through missed embassy appointments or non-compliance with documentation processes—detention centres reach the limits of their persuasive capacity. At this point, the police take over to enforce the return. The Border Police are instrumental in executing deportations, coordinating logistics through the PPS, conducting security assessments to determine escort requirements the travel logistics via PPS. If an individual cooperates and requests assistance with returning home, they might be allowed to travel alone. However, if they have exhibited ‘problematic behaviour’ (P1, D1 and D3), such as being disruptive in the detention centre, the police can arrange so that they travel with escorts for safety reasons.

Effectiveness in the return process varies among the actors involved. The detention centre staff noted that while they succeed in many cases, the police are more often the effective enforcers due to their broader powers. The Migration Agency is currently looking into expanding on their motivating methods and in doing so aim to achieve a higher utilisation of their own cases. The police's ability to enforce returns, even against resistance, currently plays a crucial role in the execution of many returns. Thus, the combined efforts of SMA, Border Police, and detention centres create a comprehensive system aimed at facilitating returns as efficiently as possible.

Noteworthy is that many civil society organizations engage in both contesting and (indirectly) facilitating actions within the return migration infrastructure, exemplified by the following actions from the Swedish Red Cross and FARR. The Red Cross can check for grounds for a new assessment or to apply for a residence permit on the grounds of impediment to enforcement. Their lawyers screen cases, represent individuals, and run cases to ensure the process is legally secure, catching those who might fall through the cracks. This exemplifies their contesting role, as they help with appeals and legal matters to support migrants' rights. On the facilitating side, the Red Cross offer return support which for example can be given in the form of material support like suitcases, travel expenses, and basic necessities such as underwear, food packages, and hygiene items. They also provide contacts in the receiving countries and traditional humanitarian aid when possible. Similarly, FARR engages in both contesting and facilitating actions. In their contesting role, they assist migrants by providing general information about their rights in detention, helping to submit applications for impediments to enforcement, and ensuring that legal provisions are upheld. In their facilitating role, FARR informs migrants about available grants and return support and conduct courses to help migrants understand and fill out necessary forms, safeguarding their ability to receive support upon return to the receiving country.

To better understand how these power dynamics unfold in practice, we will trace the complete trajectory of a detainee's experience through the detention system - from initial intake procedures to final departure - analysing how each temporal phase (arrival, assessment, preparation, and exit) serves as a distinct site of institutional "doing" where compliance is systematically negotiated.

5.2.1. Arrival to detention – enrolment interviews

The arrival process establishes the foundational power dynamics of detention. During our fieldwork, we asked detention staff about initial intake procedures - specifically about the moment when detainees are transported by vehicle to the secured garage entrance of detention facilities. Framing our inquiry from the detainee's perspective, we asked: "What should

someone expect from the moment they enter your facility until their eventual deportation?" One staff member explained:

*"...let's say you come with the NTE (The National Prison and Probation Service's Transport Unit) or with the police. Then you meet us, our staff, and then you have a so-called **arrival interview**. It's quite a massive conversation when you've been detained. Often the person is perhaps in shock. You don't know what's happening. They may have been taken from their flat in circumstances that may have been turbulent. They come to us and this conversation is then very important. Here we tell them about the detention decision, inform them about it, why they have been taken into custody. We explain rules and procedures. We tell them where they are, what the organisation actually looks like at all levels. We tell them that we have NGOs that come and hold meetings that are available to detainees. How the medical care works, what the procedures are, what the consequences are if you do not follow our rules and procedures that we have here. We also tell them how to live, what it looks like, that they share rooms and that it is with people from all over the world. You cannot choose how you want to live. We tell you about how the food is served and what times and what applies there. Asking about them, so offering assistance. That whole process really. And we also ask them how they feel about their return. That's what comes up in the first conversation" (D1)*

These interviews represent a critical interaction between detention staff and newly arrived detainees where staff explain the reasons for detention, rules, procedures, and available services. All interviewed detention staff mentioned that detainees often arrive in shock, having been abruptly removed from their homes. One staff member described the situation:

"...They don't know what's happening. They may have been taken from their flat in circumstances that may have been turbulent... Here we tell them about the detention decision, inform them about it, why they have been taken into custody." (D1).

Our interview data reveals a recurrent pattern among newly detained individuals: "claiming ignorance about their detention decision". Consequently, detention staff routinely allocate significant portions of initial intake procedures to reviewing deportation orders. As one officer explained:

"I usually say, if you don't know, we can go through it. I'll explain to you, I'll read the decision and I'll explain to you why you've been taken into custody." (D3).

The enrolment interview is also critical for setting expectations and assessing detainees' mental state. Staff conduct suicide screenings and explain detainees' rights and obligations. A supervisor described the emotional toll:

"We go through rules and procedures... There's a form called suicide screening. We ask questions that are relevant to whether a person is suicidal... It's important for us to know... Many arrive in shock—ripped from their lives, disoriented. We conduct suicide screenings because some are so desperate. One man begged, 'Just shoot me instead of sending me back.' How do you respond to that?" (D5).

Detainees are informed of their right to access healthcare services. Accordingly,

"We have a nurse who is here during office hours. You are also entitled to dental care, which costs SEK 50. You also get a daily allowance if you have no money with you. And then you also get daily recreation or employment. And then you will also be assigned a counsellor in your custody case. With whom you can also discuss questions." (D2)

Following this first arrival interview, detainees receive a “bag” with standardized supplies (like clothing, toiletries, and a phone for limited international calls), and assigned to a bed - mirroring a prison intake.

"Then you go in with the staff and you get a, what you might call it, a bag. A larger bag where you have a blanket, pillow, toothbrush. Whatever you might need. If they don't have any clothes, we can give them some from us. T-shirts, trousers, underwear, socks, slippers. You get skin care products. And if the Migration Agency assesses that there is a risk that the person might bring something that they are not allowed to bring into the department, we search the person, body search. We also search their luggage. Then the person is there." (D1)

They are shown their living quarters and introduced to facilities such as shared rooms, dining areas, and recreational spaces. In the first encounter a soft, ‘friendly’ tone is set between detention staff and the ‘new detainee’. Our interview analysis suggests that detention staff receive training to cultivate a specific institutional environment. Some accounts indicate that staff employ discursive strategies to distance themselves from deportation decisions, instead framing removal orders as purely legal decisions. This approach appears designed to encourage detainees to view staff as facilitators rather than decision-makers, while positioning detention centres as spaces where staff strive to make this final transition "as smooth as possible" within the constraints of the system.

Overall, detention arrival procedures, as outlined in arrival interviews can be seen as **doings** in detention infrastructures, aiming to orient detainees, and establish control from the onset. The system appears designed to balance operational needs with detainee welfare - offering structured support like healthcare, legal counselling, and daily activities while maintaining necessary security protocols. These procedures reflect the facility's dual role in both managing detention and preparing individuals for potential return.

5.2.2. Everyday life in detention: Balancing care and security

The daily routines in detention centres reveal a complex interplay between institutional requirements and staff-detainee interactions. As one staff member explained, *"We work with people, not machines - clarity and honesty are key in our communication."* This emphasis on interpersonal connection shapes many mundane practices within the facilities. As one officer noted, *"Our work is about finding the right balance - we must maintain security while treating people with dignity."* This dual focus shapes all aspects of daily life behind the walls.

Morning routines begin with basic needs.

"When I start my shift, it could involve anything from helping someone contact their lawyer to serving meals or arranging medical care," described a staff member. *"Some detainees want to leave immediately, others want to appeal - we try to assist however possible within the rules."*

The dining hall operates on strict schedules, with officers noting, *"We always serve meals with two staff present - it's part of our security protocol, but also a chance for regular contact."*

The material environment is designed to give the feeling of normalcy. *"We have dining rooms, laundry facilities, prayer spaces, and recreation areas,"* described one interviewee (D3), which include communal spaces for meals and socializing, recreational activities (TV rooms, sports, music activities) and communication technologies (monitored Skype/Facebook access).

The courtyard offers temporary break - *"They get three hours outside daily when weather permits, where they might play football or just sit in the sun"*. Staff organize regular activities like weekend Bingo games, with one officer noting, *"It gives them something else to think about - small prizes like sweets or shampoo make a difference"* (D3). These efforts appear genuinely aimed at alleviating stress, as another added: *"When they can request music or play guitar, you see their mood improve"* (D3).

Evening routines include room checks and preparations for the next day. *"We look in every living space before lights out"*, an officer explained (D2). *"Not just for security, but to see if anyone needs extra blankets or has health concerns"*. The same staff member reflected, *"At the end of each shift, I ask myself - did I help someone today? Even in small ways?"*

While maintaining these services, staff must balance care with security protocols. *"Our work always involves safety considerations,"* one officer stressed (D5). Security routines (food service in pairs, room checks, walking around – see the next section for dynamic security approach) are embedded in daily operations, ensuring control is ever-present, even during mundane tasks.

Box 5 - Daily life in detentions: an excerpt from an interview with an officer

"We have the dining room. We have a laundry room where they can wash their bed linen or private clothes. We have the quiet room where someone can be those who want to pray can be there. Or someone who wants to talk on the phone, talk undisturbed. We have TV rooms where they can watch TV, football or films or different things. We have computers where you can sit at computers and keep in touch with relatives via Facebook or other things. Some people also download Whatsapp which they use to communicate or Skype. We have visiting rooms where we have mounted computers where we have installed Skype so they can use it and keep track. But in the visiting rooms where we have connected to camera. Because when they are inside the computers that we have inside the shell protection, they see who they are talking to but they cannot see them. But when they are in the visiting rooms and use the computers, they can see each other because there is a camera there. So it's because of confidentiality that we don't have a camera on the others who are inside. We have the courtyard where they can spend three hours a day if they want. We have the gym where they can be and exercise.

And then we usually organise many different activities. For example, the one that comes at the top of those activities is Bingo, which we play on Saturdays. And these are activities I organise when I'm working because I think a lot of people like it. They get little prizes and everything like that. It's just sweets and shampoo and little things that they get. But still it makes them think about something else instead of that. So we do it sometimes. We have the table tennis table where they can play table tennis. We have video games where they can play. And we have. Yes, in the summers we usually organise many activities in the courtyard. For example, they can have a barbecue. They can plant different herbs or something that they use. And they can play football or basketball or something like that. We usually have YouTube on the phone there too. We have a phone that we connect to a speaker. They can request some music and we play it in the playground at a high volume where they can play. And we have guitars that they can use. I am currently talking to my managers. We have musical instruments that we have as much as possible. Which I'm holding on to and I'm having some meeting with someone now. We are going to look into it. I want to get a cupboard inside where we can have all the musical instruments. Where they can come and rent it, or to borrow. To be able to play and so on. So in the dining room. For a while here we have had troubadours who usually come once a week.

That was a long time ago. We have had such activity in the past that we have found a hairdresser who usually comes once in a while. But that was a long time ago. We don't have anyone coming now. Sometimes there are certain activities that happen sometimes. It depends on what their needs are and based on that we adapt." (D3)

This ethnographic snapshot underscores how return infrastructures operate not only through formal policies but also through the subtle, everyday "doings" of actors. The everyday routines within Sweden's detention centres reveal a carefully calibrated system where mundane activities and institutional control intertwine.

Staff emphasize communication - highlighting the importance of clarity, honesty, and language skills - as tools to ease tensions and foster cooperation, presenting themselves as mediators rather than enforcers. *"Speaking multiple languages makes a real difference,"* emphasized one multilingual officer. *"When I can explain things in someone's native tongue, you see the tension leave their face."* Another added, *"Being clear about rules actually builds trust - they know what to expect from us and what we expect from them."*

The mundane, everyday practices in detention centres create a complex relational dynamic between staff and detainees, oscillating between care and control. The interactions are framed around practical *doings* that structure daily life, yet simultaneously reinforce institutional power. Ultimately, these routine *doings* construct detention as a space of regulated temporality, where the tension between caregiving and carceral logics plays out in every interaction, shaping detainee experience.

5.2.3. 'Dynamic Security' approach

The concept of "dynamic security" represents the foundational philosophy governing daily interactions within Swedish detention facilities. As one experienced officer explained:

"Dynamic security means what we have as our tools are our senses. It's hearing, it's sight... we don't have any OC spray, we don't have any batons and we don't have anything like that for our own safety. But what is good is that we get to work more with the relationships. And I think that's very positive about working in a detention centre is that you can come in and feel that you can make a difference." (D1)

Here the emphasis on "senses" points at relying on observation and communication rather than other security tools. This requires proactive engagement, where staff assess detainees' moods and intervene before conflicts escalate. This approach creates a unique environment where security is maintained primarily through constant staff presence and interpersonal engagement rather than physical restraints. Unlike traditional prison systems that rely on coercive tools (batons, pepper spray, isolation), this model prioritizes constant staff presence, verbal de-escalation, and interpersonal understanding as primary security mechanisms. Officers describe their daily routines as:

"We move around among the detainees. We're friendly, we're respectful, but we're not really friends. But we are here for them if they need help. We help them within the limits we can." (D2)

Staff maintain approachable, yet professional boundaries. This dual role (helper/authority figure) allows officers to exert influence while avoiding overt coercion.

The system relies heavily on staff's ability to read situations and intervene verbally before conflicts escalate. Without traditional prison measures, staff must negotiate compliance through dialogue. As one supervisor noted:

"It's also just that we don't have a prison service, we can't lock people up as we please. Something has to happen before we can separate someone. So in this dynamic security, it's probably that they'll still feel that we're doing what we can." (D2)

However, this approach presents significant challenges. Staff report feeling vulnerable without traditional security tools. Some desire additional security measures, revealing tensions between humanitarian ideals and on-the-ground risks. *"For our safety, I usually say we have only the body and our mouth to be able to talk. And that's all we have in terms of security."* (D3)

The tension between these perspectives underscores the fundamental contradictions inherent in detention systems that aspire to be both secure and humane. Despite its progressive framing, *dynamic security* does not eliminate power imbalances, it reconfigures them. Detainees may experience fewer overtly punitive measures, but the psychological effects of constant monitoring and dependency on staff persist. As one officer noted: *"It's good in theory, but many colleagues wish for more security tools."* (D3) This tension reflects a broader dilemma: Can detention ever be truly humane when its ultimate purpose is forced removal? Dynamic security attempts to soften the process but cannot resolve this core paradox. The emphasis on communication and presence humanizes daily interactions, yet the end goal – return/deportation- remains unchanged, raising questions about the limits of "soft" carceral control.

5.2.3. Return counselling in detentions

Return counselling in Swedish detention centres operates at the intersection of case management, psychological persuasion, and coercive bureaucracy (cf. "Paperwork Performances" by A. Lindberg and L-M. Borrelli, 2024). The practice is framed as a humanitarian alternative to forced deportation, yet remains fundamentally geared toward ensuring compliance with removal orders. Through extended staff interviews, several key themes emerge regarding its techniques, effectiveness, and underlying contradictions.

The counselling process begins almost immediately after detention, as described by one officer:

"If it's our own case, the case officers meet them as soon as they're back on duty. The day after. So the return work starts quite immediately, really. And I would say that it already starts at the time of enrolment, because then we ask the question: how do you see your own return?" (D1)

This proactive engagement establishes return as an inevitability, framing detention as a transitional space rather than a site of legal contestation. The question *"How do you see your own return?"* (a question asked in these interviews) superficially invites agency but presupposes removal as the only viable outcome.

In detention centres, the tone of motivational interviews becomes increasingly direct and clear as case officers escalate the sense of urgency. These interviews frame compliance as inevitable, emphasizing the necessity of preparation for return. Another key objective of these interviews

in detention is to encourage detainees to accept their deportation orders and leave Sweden voluntarily.

Counselling employs a carrot-and-stick approach, and blends positive reinforcement (e.g. reintegration support, practical assistance) with implicit threats (police enforcement, prolonged detention). One officer outlines the stark choice presented to detainees:

"Now you have two choices: go home with us, we'll take you to the airport and wave you off, or tomorrow we'll hand your case over to the police, and the police can, if necessary, drag you out of here and put you on a plane. Those are the two options—now it's time to decide. So, it becomes much clearer and then some people choose to buy or to say that you can book a trip for me, they say." (MV-1)

This binary framing - cooperate for a "dignified" departure or face forcible removal - reveals the performative voluntarism of the system. While staff emphasize clarity and transparency, the power imbalance renders the choice largely illusory. This framing leverages detainees' fear of police enforcement to encourage compliance. However, when cooperation stalls, cases are transferred to the Border Police, shifting from "soft" to "hard" enforcement.

Some officers adopt a future-oriented approach, "planting ideas" of economic or social reintegration to make return palatable:

"I know one guy—you speak Swedish so damn well, I said, why? Swedes often go on holiday to Tunisia. Have you never thought about the guide thing? Make a website, be a driver, guide, interpreter. Swedes love that sort of thing. But then I was a bit happy when I heard somewhere that someone had had contact with him from the others who work here. That he actually did. He did start one. And then, it's more like one of those seeds that we're trying to plant, it can be one of those things that you work with, or that we fix this with English lessons. We have someone who has worked as a teacher before, and so we fix, because it's no problem to buy materials if an idea is sown. We used to have someone who was in charge of the activities when it was an organised activity. Did a lot of music, organised instruments and things like that" (D2)

Such narratives reframe return as an opportunity rather than a failure, appealing to detainees' aspirations. However, these anecdotes of success (e.g., a former detainee starting a tourism business) are exceptional rather than systemic. The emphasis on individual entrepreneurship obscures structural barriers to reintegration, such as lack of state support or unstable conditions in countries of origin. This example also illustrates how counselling - aimed at persuading detainees to accept voluntary return - is not confined to formal interviews but permeates everyday conversations and interactions within detention centres.

Not all detainees are receptive to counselling. Non-cooperation -whether due to distrust, fear, or legal resistance- often triggers escalation to police enforcement:

"When you're in the Migration Agency's case, and when you've reached that point where it's not possible [to secure cooperation], the Migration Agency usually hands the case over to the police." (D3)

The police, in contrast to SMA staff, adopt a minimalist, enforcement-focused approach: *"The police say, you just have to leave the country, and we'll make sure you do it at the end, that's it." (D3)*. According to the same officer for SMA-led counselling, there are other perspectives that come in.

“...you are so much connected to the case itself. And when you work in a detention centre, as I usually say, you have to know the case, how the case has developed, because you go back to the day the person applied for asylum, how the case has developed, and what has happened to make you end up in detention. So that you look at the whole picture. But the police are not interested in that...” (D3)

This shift underscores the asymmetry of "voluntary" return: detainees may engage with counselling to avoid police intervention, but the threat of force looms throughout the process. Detention as an infrastructure facilitates also a shift in counselling modalities, moving from prolonged “negotiation” to streamlined “coercion”. An officer reflected on this:

"In the beginning when I was working, I thought that the Migration Agency was extremely inefficient in working with their cases. It took a long time to get them enforced. They had four, five, six and seven return counselling sessions. It was like, please, can't you go home? At that level. Now you don't work with as much patience, which I think is good, but you talk a bit more in clearly, which I like from the authority I came from, the prison and probation service. You have a conversation, you present the expectations from there, then maybe you have maximum an another one, where you say if this doesn't happen blah blah blah, then we think we can't execute your case on a voluntary basis. Then we have to hand you over to the police and then this happens. Some people might be a bit frightened by this, as they don't want to come to their home countries with a piece of paper saying that the police have sent them home. Because they think they might not be well received there." (D4)

The officer who has previously worked in Prison and Probation Services contrasts past practices - characterized by repeated, almost pleading return counselling sessions (*"please, can't you go home?"*) - with current methods that adopt clearer ultimatums borrowed from other authorities (e.g. prison-style communication). The remark about detainees fearing police documentation exposes how deportation methods carry real consequences beyond borders, potentially affecting reintegration. This account demonstrates how administrative "streamlining" often translates to hardened enforcement, where detainees face quicker escalation to police involvement under the guise of procedural “clarity”.

The counselling process reveals fundamental tensions between actors. SMA officers frame their interviews as pragmatic guidance: *"We show them the statistics - maybe 5% of appeals succeed. Then we say: 'Let's plan your return properly with reintegration support, not gamble on miracles.'" (MV-1)*. However, non-governmental actors usually counter that this approach coerces consent. As one of the NGO representatives stated: *"Presenting return as the only 'rational' choice ignores real dangers. We've documented 14 cases where our legal interventions prevented wrongful deportations to active war zones."* (CSO-F-1). Detention staff express frustration with NGOs' close scrutiny, framing this as one of the obstacles in front of return operations: *"You'll have someone ready to board the plane, then an NGO lawyer shows up with last-minute appeals. Suddenly we're the villains for following the law."* (D2)

Return counselling in detention centres exemplifies soft coercion, a doing designed to produce compliance through dialogue rather than brute force. While staff emphasize clarity, patience, and reintegration support, the process remains tethered to an inescapable outcome: removal. The tension between care and control is unresolved, as even the most persuasive techniques cannot disguise the fundamental power imbalance. As one officer concedes, *"The basic idea of all talks is that they should motivate the detainee to want to go home"* (D4). This analysis

suggests that while dynamic security and return counselling humanize detention in theory, they ultimately serve to legitimize expulsion by framing it as a collaborative process.

5.2.4. Document preparation

A significant portion of detention efforts focuses on securing travel documents - a process that hinges entirely on cooperation from both detainees and their countries of origin. This bureaucratic endeavour often becomes a protracted struggle, revealing the asymmetrical power dynamics inherent in forced return systems. Caseworkers spend weeks negotiating with foreign missions, facing outright refusal when detainees resist. As one officer noted:

"For a while it was also like if you want a document from Iraqi embassy. Then it was more like the officials at the embassy started asking the Iraqi detainee, 'do you want to go back to Iraq? Do you want to go home?' If an Iraqi detainee said 'no' to returning, embassy officials would immediately stop assisting. That was the end of it." (D2)

For countries like Eritrea, which refuse to issue documents, authorities resort to lengthy alternatives like fingerprint matching (MV-1) - a testament to the systemic barriers embedded in deportation regimes.

As discussed above, the state authorities use different methods (e.g. return liaison officers) and technologies (e.g. data forensics, such as analysing phone records, money transfers, social media traffic⁴⁸) to prepare travel documents, or establish one's country of origin. Yet these workarounds cannot mask a fundamental tension: while states deploy expansive resources to enforce removal, detainees wield what little agency they have through strategic non-cooperation. As staff observed: *"They'll swear they're from a village that doesn't exist, knowing it buys them months" (D3)*

The document chase epitomizes the broader detention paradox where bureaucracy functions as both a control mechanism and a site of resistance.

Table 2 - 'Doings' in Detention Centres by Different Actors

Doings	Actor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Conducting motivational interviews ● Preparing travel documents ● Coordinating with embassies ● Translating birth/school records 	SMA / case officers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementing dynamic security, e.g. maintaining security through presence and dialogue, handling crises ● Managing daily operations, providing basic services ● Escorting to appointments 	Detention Staff
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enforcing deportations ● Conducting security assessments ● Coordinating/Executing forced returns 	Border Police
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Arranging escorts 	Prison & Probation Service
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing legal aid ● Connecting with origin countries ● Monitoring conditions ● Offering reintegration support 	CSOs (Red Cross, FARR etc.)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing healthcare, ● Conducting mental health assessments 	Medical Staff

⁴⁸ For example, *"When Algeria refused documents, we found the detainee's uncle via Facebook who provided family records" (CSO-F-1)*

5.2.5. Exit from detention

For individuals in detention, several distinct exit routes exist, each reflecting different facets of the state's approach to migration control. The first two are ended with no-deportation, whereas the other two options differ by actors' involvement and the tools used.

1. Detainees may exit detention by successfully appealing their deportation order. This legal pathway represents the only formal mechanism for challenging the state's removal decision, though such victories remain statistically rare in practice.
2. Under current Swedish Asylum Law, the maximum detention period is 12 months (extendable to 24 months for individuals with criminal convictions). However, if deportation is unenforceable (due to lack of travel documents, non-cooperation by the home country, or no third country accepting the individual), detainees will be released. Under current Swedish law, detention cannot continue indefinitely if deportation is unfeasible. However, the EU's proposed Return Regulation could change this by allowing longer detention periods or stricter supervision.
3. The final stage of deportation reveals significant differences in how Swedish authorities enforce removals. When SMA manages the process, officers accompany detainees to the airport and ensure they board their flight, departing only once the plane is airborne. "*We just accompany them to the airport... when the plane has taxied out, we leave,*" explains one official (MV1). This approach maintains a procedural tone, avoiding overt displays of coercion.
4. The most coercive exit occurs through police-led removals. Police-led deportations operate differently, with two distinct methods: escorted and unescorted removals. In escorted cases, officers physically accompany detainees from detention all the way to their destination country, ensuring compliance throughout the journey. Unescorted removals, while still enforced, allow detainees to travel without constant police supervision (in the plane) once certain conditions are met. Unescorted removals are decided case by case.

PPS plays a key logistical role in both systems, particularly for police-coordinated deportations. PPS officers handle secure transport to airports and, when required, provide additional personnel for high-risk removals. Their involvement ensures that deportations adhere to security protocols while attempting to minimize confrontational scenarios.

The Police and PPS when escorting a detainee for deportation, they follow strict protocols. Handcuffs are routinely used during transport to/from vehicles and in public airport areas, but their continuous use depends on risk assessment: "*For compliant detainees, we may remove cuffs once seated on the plane*" (P1). Alternative restraints like waist chains or leg irons are used exceptionally for high-risk cases.

Another procedure followed during the "exit" is pre-departure medical screening. Mandatory checks are conducted 24-48 hours before flight. These checks are based on basic physical examination by detention centre medical staff. If the detainee has a suicidal potential or self-harm risk, mental health evaluation is also conducted. Procedures include also contingency plans for unfit-to-fly cases (e.g., pregnancy complications, acute illness). For instance, a case officer noted "*We've halted deportations when doctors certify travel would endanger life*" (MV1- memo).

There are also airport and in-flight protocols. Particularly for enforced removals, discreet routes, such as the use of private terminals and service entrances are used. Deportations are often scheduled for early morning or late-night flights to minimize public exposure. If it is an escorted removal, there are onboard procedures, such as two officers minimum per detainee on commercial flights, and pre-coordination with airline crew on seating and emergency protocols. According to Police Transport Unit guideline, emergency exits in the plane kept free. Escort team in regular deportations consists of two uniformed officers and an interpreter if needed. In high-risk cases, additional medical personnel and/or PPS specialists join the escort team.

Recent court rulings have limited restraint use after a 2021 case where excessive force caused injury. New guidelines require proportionality assessments for each restraint method, mandatory body camera footage during transports and independent monitoring of sensitive cases.⁴⁹

These exit pathways reveal Sweden's graduated approach to expulsion—from judicial reprieve to various forms of state-enforced removal. The system's architecture demonstrates how detention functions as both a holding mechanism and a pressure tool to encourage departure, with the threat of police enforcement looming over all 'voluntary' processes. Current debates about detention duration limits under proposed EU regulations may significantly alter this landscape in coming years.

5.2.6. The doings of CSOs in detention centres

Non-state actors play a multifaceted and often contentious role in Sweden's detention centres. While the SMA and police focus on enforcing deportations, NGOs operate in the gaps, providing legal aid, monitoring human rights compliance, and contesting the increased use of detention as a tool to enforce returns. Their work ranges from direct humanitarian assistance to systemic advocacy, often putting them at odds with state authorities, and navigating the contradictions of a system designed for removal.

In terms of doings, CSOs provide critical legal support to detainees, helping them navigate complex asylum and deportation procedures. This includes filing appeals against detention and monitoring detention conditions. For instance, lawyers working in different NGOs scrutinize detention orders for procedural errors, arguing for release or alternative measures, such as the "supervision" method. They also assist with last-minute appeals, particularly in cases where returnees might face persecution in their home country. One of the NGO representatives noted:

"We've seen cases where detention was extended unlawfully because the SMA didn't properly assess individual circumstances. Our legal interventions have secured releases in over a third of contested cases." (CSO-F-1)

An experienced lawyer who provided legal support for detainees for many years provided a similar account:

⁴⁹ Information for this section is gathered partly from interviews and partly from secondary sources, such as Swedish Police Authority directives (2023) and ECRE deportation monitoring data.

"The Migration Agency tells detainees, 'You have no chance', but we've won appeals for clients from Afghanistan, Iraq, and Eritrea. Hope isn't 'false'—it's a legal right." (L1).

In detention interviews, CSOs attempt to humanize a process obsessed with paperwork. "Case officers should listen first—understand lives here and the realities people would return to" (CSO-F-1) argues one advocate, criticizing the myopic focus on passports and threats of reduced allowances. They describe families fractured by arbitrary definitions of "cooperation": a father deported to Kazakhstan and likely imprisoned, a mother stranded with children in Sweden, both embassies refusing documents. "They claim she isn't cooperating, but she's attended every interview, contacted embassies, stayed at a known address for years." (CSO-F-1). The CSO representative we interviewed was quite critical about the bureaucracy's indifference to what he called "limbo by design" (CSO-F-1). The same respondent shared with us his experience with a return interview where a caseworker mocked the advocate present, "patronizing remarks to show who had power" (CSO-F-1).

Beyond legal battles, CSOs provide essential services to improve detainees' well-being. For example, many non-state actors, such as Red Cross, Church of Sweden provide psychosocial support in terms counselling for trauma, isolation, and the stress of indefinite detention. CSOs also provide material aid, such as distributing clothing, hygiene kits, and phone credits to help detainees maintain family contact. As one volunteer noted, "Detainees get €5 a day for essentials. We bring extra socks, toothpaste, books—small things that restore a bit of dignity." (CSO-C-1)

Another area CSOs are active is medical advocacy, that is, pushing for proper healthcare access, especially for vulnerable groups (pregnant women, torture survivors). For example, a CSO representative noted:

"We had a detainee who attempted suicide after his third deportation order. Our psychologists intervened, and finally, the SMA acknowledged his mental health crisis—but only after we threatened legal action." (CSO-RC-1)

CSOs act as independent watchdogs, documenting abuses and pushing for policy reforms. Some of the CSOs (e.g. Amnesty International) publish reports, exposing prolonged detention, poor conditions, and violations of due process, and lobby for alternatives to detention, especially for families and children. They also engage with the media to make detainee voices heard in order to shape public opinion. As one CSO member noted:

"Our 2023 report revealed that 60% of detainees were held beyond the legal review period. The government dismissed it, but the UN cited it in their critique of Sweden." (CSO-AI-1)

Some of the CSOs focus area (e.g. Red Cross) is preparing detainees for life after deportation, particularly when return is inevitable. We can note their pre-departure counselling as doings from an RMI perspective. These counselling includes helping detainees contact family, secure housing, or find work in their home countries; providing luggage, travel funds, and starter kits (e.g., small business grants). Within this scope, they also conduct post-return monitoring, ensuring returnees are not persecuted or left destitute. A CSO worker gave us an example: "We connected a Somali returnee with a local cooperative. He's now running a small shop—better than being dumped at Mogadishu airport with nothing." (CSO-RC-1). Another NGO representative mentioned a seemingly small, but meaningful act: "Forced returns to

Afghanistan are unethical, but when they happen, we at least ensure someone meets them at the airport." (CSO-F-1)

The most politically charged role of CSOs is their opposition to detention as a policy. Although in the current political climate, their oppositional voices are not visible, we should add this in CSO's portfolio of doings. All CSO representatives we interviewed commonly underlined that detention is inherently traumatic and ineffective for facilitating returns. Instead they suggested promoting the supervision (*uppsikt*) model. As one representative of a research-policy institute noted: *"Detention doesn't increase deportations—it just makes them more brutal. Our data shows supervised compliance works better."* (CSO-D-1).

CSOs are also engaged with taking cases to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR). For instance, a CSO worker mentioned to us: *"We're suing Sweden over the detention of children. The government knows it's illegal, but they keep doing it."* (CSO-SC-1)

CSOs occupy a paradoxical position within Sweden's detention system - simultaneously sustaining its operations through service provision while contesting its fundamental legitimacy. By delivering legal aid, monitoring conditions, and advocating for detainee rights, they introduce crucial accountability mechanisms into an otherwise asymmetrical power structure. However, this dual role generates institutional friction, as many detention staff perceive CSO interventions as undermining enforcement priorities. These complex state-CSO dynamics, which reveal the contested nature of migration control, will be examined in depth in Section 5.4 (Relations).

5.3. Materials and technologies used in detention centres

The Swedish detention system operates through a complex interplay of material resources, technologies, and human interactions, all of which are deeply embedded in the broader RMI. We will discuss materialities and technologies under five categories: Architectural, technological, administrative, everyday tools and human resources.

Detention centres employ various materials and technologies to ensure security and provide necessary amenities for detainees. Unlike prisons, these centres do not use pepper spray, restraints, or batons. Instead, they are designed, as one staff portrayed, more along the lines of "a large hostel" with alarms on windows, locked doors to the outside and surveillance cameras in the public spaces. Staff members move around the facility, offering both security and assistance, ensuring that detainees stay within the premises and have access to necessary services and interactions.

From the outset, it is important to emphasize that many of the practices ("doings") discussed earlier inherently involve materialities and the deployment of diverse technologies. Furthermore, it is crucial to recognize that any material or technology implemented not only serves its immediate purpose but also actively shapes the infrastructure itself. These elements exist in a co-constitutive relationship, meaning that the design and functioning of detention infrastructures are continually influenced by the materialities and technologies embedded within them.

Viewed through this lens, the materialities and technologies employed in detention infrastructures reflect the inherent duality of Sweden's broader return migration infrastructures. This duality lies in the ongoing balance - or tension - between securitization imperatives and human rights considerations. The ways in which materials and technologies

are utilized reveal how these competing priorities manifest in practice, shaping both the physical environment and the lived experiences of detainees.

At the heart of this system lies the *central database* managed by SMA, which serves as a critical tool for tracking and managing information about all asylum applicants and detainees. This database allows limited access to other authorities, such as the police, who can retrieve specific details about an individual's status or case. While the SMA maintains exclusive control over data entry and management, the database exemplifies how technology is leveraged to enforce administrative oversight while balancing privacy concerns. However, staff emphasize that the true resource within detention centres is not technological but rather the collective knowledge, experience, and multilingual capabilities of the workforce. These **human resources** play a pivotal role in facilitating communication, reducing tensions, and navigating the complexities of detainee interactions, as discussed broadly in the section about "dynamic security".

Architectural designs also shape the detention environment, creating spaces that aim to balance security with a semblance of normalcy. Facilities resemble large hostels, equipped with alarms on windows, locked external doors, and surveillance cameras in public areas. Inside, detainees live in shared or single rooms and have access to communal spaces like dining halls, courtyards, and recreational areas. Segregation units are used for individuals deemed disruptive or at risk of self-harm, furnished with safety measures such as soft cutlery to prevent harm. These architectural choices reflect an effort to create controlled environments that appear humane yet ultimately serve the purpose of enforcing removal decisions. The dynamic security model further underscores this balance, relying on constant staff presence and interpersonal engagement rather than physical restraints. Staff move among detainees, offering both assistance and supervision, embodying the philosophy of "being friendly but not friends".

Technological tools extend beyond databases and architectural features to include communication systems that connect detainees with the outside world. Skype-enabled visiting rooms allow detainees to maintain contact with family members under supervised conditions, while computers and internet access provide opportunities for education and recreation. Despite these provisions, challenges persist due to systemic gaps and operational limitations. For instance, contraband occasionally enters facilities due to insufficient visitor checks, and staff shortages strain daily operations. Moreover, the absence of traditional security tools, as mentioned by one of the staff: "*We have nothing in terms of security tools—no pepper spray, no batons. All we have are our senses and our ability to talk,*" (D1) underscore the tensions and limitations within the system.

Administrative processes form another cornerstone of detention materialities, shaping how authority is exercised and experienced. Upon arrival, detainees undergo comprehensive enrolment interviews where staff explain the reasons for detention, rules, procedures, and available services. These sessions often involve suicide screenings and explanations of rights and obligations, setting the tone for the detainee's stay. Throughout their time in detention, individuals are subjected to motivational interviews designed to encourage voluntary return. Case officers frame compliance as a pragmatic choice, leveraging detainees' fear of police enforcement to elicit cooperation. When voluntary return fails, cases are escalated to the Border Police, marking a shift from "soft" to "hard" enforcement. This bureaucratic machinery relies heavily on documentation (paperwork), deadlines, and statistical reports to dissuade appeals and hasten deportations.

Everyday tools, though seemingly mundane, play a significant role in maintaining order and providing basic necessities. From soft cutlery in segregation rooms to projectors for watching films, these items underscore the dual objectives of safety and comfort. Basic medical services, educational opportunities, and recreational activities like sports, games and gardening further contribute to the perception of normalcy. Yet, beneath this veneer lies the reality of confinement - a paradox acknowledged even by staff, who describe the facilities as neither prisons nor hostels but something in between.

Human resources remain the backbone of the detention system, with multilingual and experienced teams facilitating smoother interactions and reducing cultural misunderstandings. The real resource highlighted by staff is their collective knowledge and experience:

"In my opinion, it is knowledge about about about yes. So that's the biggest resource that we have, both for example yes, and from language to like experiences. We have staff with different experiences and working with different things. This is the biggest resource that exists at the detention centre and at each workplace, I think. And then of course office supplies. We have computers, paper? Pens?" (D5)

Unlike physical tools or databases, this resource is intangible yet crucial. It enables staff to handle challenges effectively, adapt to unique cases, and maintain the dynamic security model that relies heavily on interpersonal engagement.

Language skills, in particular, enable staff to build trust with detainees, making the “*job easier*” for everyone involved. However, the reliance on dialogue and interpersonal engagement comes with its own set of challenges. Staff express frustration over their limited tools and the political pressures that shape their work. The lack of streamlined search protocols and shifting government policies create operational instability, leaving frontline workers to navigate ethical dilemmas and systemic inefficiencies.

Another important aspect of human resources is the introduction of MRBR (Misconduct and Criminal Records) checks for detention staff which represents a technological advancement aimed at enhancing internal security and trust by ensuring that staff do not pose a threat to detainees or the facility.

During the interviews, detention staff expressed differing opinions on the need for additional materials and techniques to manage the changing environment. A manager highlighted that while staff are mentally prepared, the absence of certain legal supports and an increasingly tougher clientele and higher-security detainees pose challenges. The manager stressed the need for more segregation rooms to handle the increasing number of detainees with violent backgrounds. Another staff member, emphasized the importance of communication and service-mindedness in their work. They expressed satisfaction with the current approach of using dialogue over physical restraints, saying, *"You should be able to talk to people. You should be able to have a dialogue with them."* However, they acknowledged that some colleagues desire additional security tools such as restraints, batons, or pepper spray, understanding their perspective but advocating for a balance between security and humane treatment. Yet another staff member pointed out the limitations in current practices, noting that while improvements may be underway, there is still a lack of essential tools for efficient and legally sound operations. For instance, due to legal requirements staff face constraints in conducting searches, necessitating “reasonable suspicion” before taking action. This limits

their ability to pre-emptively address security risks. They mentioned that staff recruited from the prison service brought valuable expertise but lacked the tools they were accustomed to, thus feeling constrained. They also highlighted the need for more comprehensive training to handle new tools and procedures, such as the ability to conduct body searches and inspect personal belongings for contraband. They criticized the current system's bureaucratic hurdles, which impede effective operations, contrasting it with the prison service's more streamlined procedures. *"There are too many decisions to be able to work effectively"* they remarked, stressing the need for a balance between operational efficiency and respecting personal integrity.

Transportation to and from the detention centres are done either via the Prison and Probation Service or the detention staff themselves via their designated vehicles. PSS use specialized vehicles (e.g. vans or buses) designed for secure transportation, similar to those used for prisoner transfers. SMA/detention staff use standard vehicles (e.g., vans, minibuses, or cars) designated for official use when transporting detainees to hospitals or embassy visits. High-security transports (e.g., deportations, individuals deemed high-risk) are realised by SPSS' specialized vehicles.

Table 3 - Materialities, Technologies and Methods in Detention

Category	Examples	Strategic Use
Architectural	Segregation rooms, locked doors, alarm systems, shared/single rooms with communal spaces	Creating controlled environments while maintaining humane appearance
Technological	Surveillance cameras, Skype visiting systems, central database, special computers and telephones, special and official transport vehicles	Monitoring while allowing limited contact with outside world
Administrative	Enrolment and motivational interviews, body search protocols, incident reporting, travel document preparation, procedural assessments	Formalizing control through bureaucratic processes
Everyday Tools	Soft cutlery, pro basic necessities (clothing, toiletries, phone credits)	Preventing harm while maintaining security
Human Resources	Multilingual staff, knowledge, dynamic security approach	Facilitating communication and reducing tensions

Flows of funding, databases, materials between these actors and networks

In recent years, the three agencies have enhanced their collaborative efforts, particularly following the critical evaluation of the State Treasury's 2020 report. In addition to the *co-location* strategy, these agencies *exchange data* and bolster their interagency collaboration through projects funded by the AMIF. (see SMA's database shared with the Police)

Each governmental agency receives its annual budget from the government, which is determined and organized according to governmental appropriation directives. Joint activities and material sharing among these agencies primarily occur through projects (usually funded

by AMIF, ERRIN, and the government). The Migration Agency's engagement with CSOs also occurs within the framework of similar project structures. In the absence of such collaborative initiatives, each entity operates independently.

In conclusion, the Swedish detention system represents a delicate equilibrium between control and care, achieved through a combination of architectural design, technological innovation, administrative processes, everyday tools, and human expertise. While the system strives to uphold humanitarian principles, it remains fundamentally rooted in the logic of enforcement. The interplay of these elements highlights the contradictions inherent in detention infrastructures: they aspire to be secure yet humane, efficient yet compassionate. Addressing the implementation gaps and power dynamics within this system requires a multifaceted approach that prioritizes transparency, accountability, and meaningful collaboration among all actors involved.

5.4. Relations between actors: Collaboration and Conflict/Contestation

Relations Between State Actors

Formal collaborations exist between agencies, such as co-location initiatives where SMA, police, and Probation Service share workspaces to streamline deportations. These arrangements aim to reduce bureaucratic delays, with one official noting, "*The co-location method is praised for facilitating shorter contact paths and easier exchange of information*" (MV-1). Communication flows between detention centres, SMA, and the police are frequent, though they often oscillate between logistical coordination and deeper discussions about operational challenges. For instance, staff describe how they handle placements for detainees being moved to other facilities, involving direct contact with counterparts in different locations. These relationships are not merely transactional; they also include informal networks built on trust and experience, such as longstanding connections between team leaders across cities. However, these collaborative efforts are undermined by broader systemic issues, including bureaucratic delays and political interference. Staff express frustration over the prolonged processing times for deportations, which they attribute to overlapping legal procedures, appeals, and enforcement obstacles. This inefficiency is compounded by political rhetoric that oversimplifies the complexities of migration management, as highlighted by one staff member's critique of populist narratives propagated by politicians. This tension underscores institutional opacity and competing priorities, where even insiders struggle to pinpoint root causes. The lack of clarity regarding accountability within the system - whether due to misplaced sympathy among SMA staff or structural bottlenecks - further complicates inter-agency relations. While there is an acknowledgment of shared goals, such as reducing costs and expediting returns, the reality is marred by institutional opacity and competing priorities.

Peer relations among detention staff

Peer relations among detention staff are shaped by the emotionally taxing nature of their work and the need for mutual support in navigating its challenges. Working in an environment where liberty is restricted creates what one staff member describes as a "negative field", characterized by pervasive tension and frustration. To mitigate these effects, staff emphasize the importance of open dialogue, camaraderie, and structured reflection mechanisms like After Action Reviews (AARs). These reviews serve as a platform for collectively analysing

incidents, and identifying areas for improvement. As noted by a team manager: *"We sit and talk together... What did we do well? How could we have done it better? And how do we spread it further?"* (D1) Such initiatives foster a sense of unity among detention staff, enabling them to manage the emotional spill over from detainees' distress more effectively (D1, D2).

Leadership plays a critical role in maintaining morale, with team leaders prioritizing the well-being of their staff by ensuring they remain mentally and physically intact both during and after shifts. Informal bonds also emerge naturally, particularly given the small teams working night shifts, where hierarchical distinctions are often set aside, as one staff noted *"Titles are usually put to one side"* (D2). Despite these supportive structures, the job remains fraught with ethical dilemmas and personal struggles. Staff recount instances where empathy for detainees blurs professional boundaries, requiring careful navigation (D2, D3). For example, developing personal connections with detainees or feeling compelled by shared cultural backgrounds can create conflicts of interest, necessitating clear communication and boundary-setting. Through these dynamics, peer relations become a cornerstone of coping and sustaining operations in an inherently challenging environment.

Relations with Healthcare Workers and Non-State Actors

Relations with healthcare workers and non-state actors (including collaborations with religious communities, e.g. the Church of Sweden). While they generally welcome any religious community that reaches out to them, they do not actively seek out such collaborations themselves. However, these communities do not contact detention centres frequently, resulting in relatively limited engagement.

Healthcare providers operate under strict medical confidentiality rules, which sometimes clash with the informational needs of detention staff. Unlike the Prison and Probation Service, where nurses are directly employed and share limited health information through informal channels, detention centre staff rely on external healthcare personnel (employed by county councils) who prioritize patient privacy. This arrangement creates friction, as one staff argued: *"We want information from the nurse about whether there is any particular disease, but he is very cautious, or she is very cautious about disclosing it, because it is with medical confidentiality."* (D4) Some staff suggest that employing dedicated medical personnel within the detention system could streamline communication and improve outcomes, though this proposal raises concerns about compromising patient rights.

Interactions with non-state actors and advocacy groups are equally nuanced. While CSOs provide essential services like legal aid, psychosocial support, and reintegration assistance, their presence is often met with ambivalence by detention staff. On one hand, detention staff recognize the value of these contributions in addressing gaps left by state agencies. On the other hand, they perceive CSO interventions—such as last-minute appeals or public campaigns highlighting alleged abuses—as disruptive and undermining enforcement efforts: *"They want to come and have views on how we do things... They're not interested in how we work."* (D2). Tensions arise when CSOs challenge the legitimacy of detention practices or file appeals against deportation orders. Detention staff frequently express irritation over what they perceive as CSOs undermining enforcement efforts: *"These NGOs come in, file appeals at the last minute, and disrupt the whole process. Then we're left dealing with angry detainees who think they've found a loophole."* (D2)

This sentiment highlights staff frustration with the perception that CSOs create *false hope* among detainees, complicating enforcement efforts. Similarly, authorities accuse some CSOs, such as Amnesty International, of bias and amplifying grievances without engaging constructively: "*Amnesty... sees us as real bastards... They cannot be better off under the circumstances than they are here, but they are desperate to make us look [bad]*" (D5). CSOs, on the other hand, argue that authorities prioritize bureaucratic processes over individual needs, particularly in detention and return cases: "*Often there is instead a focus on... the authority's needs... Whereas we see a huge need to work with the individual's needs.*" (CSO-RB). Detention staff, in turn, express frustration when CSOs provide detainees with incomplete information or delay inevitable deportations through endless paperwork: "*The NGOs say they 'prepare' people for return, but sometimes they just delay the inevitable with endless paperwork*" (D3). Authorities view certain CSOs as adversarial, as ideological adversaries, accusing them of promoting open-border policies that allegedly obstruct deportation regimes. As one police official asserted: "*These groups want open borders. If we followed their advice, no one would ever be deported.*" (P1). Such accusations underscore the deep mistrust between state and non-state actors, rooted in differing priorities and worldviews - where state actors equate border control with sovereignty, while CSOs prioritize human rights protections.

Communication gaps between detention staff and civil society organizations (CSOs) further exacerbate tensions. CSOs report sporadic engagement with authorities, where their input is occasionally welcomed but frequently overlooked in broader policy discussions. For example, Save the Children notes inconsistent responsiveness—while *minor* operational concerns may be addressed, *major* policy issues, such as those related to return centres, often face resistance. This resistance appears linked to the political sensitivity of such policies, limiting CSOs' ability to influence critical decisions despite their expertise. Beyond procedural barriers, deeper ideological divides shape these dynamics. Caritas critiques the Western-centric approach to migration policy, arguing that it neglects the complex motivations behind migration, leading to ineffective or short-sighted solutions. A more pointed critique comes from a lawyer respondent (L1), who highlights systemic flaws within the SMA, particularly in asylum assessments and the politicization of deportations—especially in volatile contexts like Afghanistan. The lawyer expresses frustration over decision-makers' lack of experience but acknowledges the difficulty of driving systemic change. Together, these critiques reveal a fundamental disconnect between policy implementation rooted in political priorities and a more nuanced, humanitarian understanding of migration.

Despite these clashes, there are moments of constructive engagement (e.g. SMA's *letter of intent* with the Swedish Red Cross; SMA engagement with Caritas for guidance on designing voluntary return programs), particularly when CSOs facilitate family reunifications or post-return monitoring. SMA itself acknowledges that differing viewpoints are inherent in its collaboration with voluntary organizations like the Red Cross. They maintain that while these organizations have their own missions and approaches, mutual respect and understanding prevail. SMA officers asserts that these differences do not limit their operations or the operations of their partners, but rather contribute to a more comprehensive approach to handling return migration. The Border Police and SMA formally welcome engagement with 'major' organizations (e.g., the Red Cross, Save the Children, and Amnesty International), framing dissenting perspectives as valuable inputs for procedural refinement. As one SMA official noted: "*We may disagree fundamentally, but we never refuse discussion with any*

stakeholder." However, this rhetoric of constructive engagement belies an operational reality where such dialogues rarely translate into substantive policy changes or improved detention conditions. Overall, these relationships reflect the broader struggle to reconcile humanitarian principles with the pragmatic demands of migration control, illustrating the intricate interplay of power, ethics, and accountability within Sweden's detention infrastructure.

5.5. Implementation gaps

Sweden's detention system operates at the intersection of migration control, bureaucratic efficiency, and human rights, revealing critical gaps between policy objectives and operational realities. Drawing on interviews with detention staff, CSOs, and legal experts, this analysis identifies several key areas. We will start with implementation gaps from the perspective of detention staff and evolve our discussion with the insights of CSOs and legal experts whom we interviewed.

In general, detention staff interviewed seem to be satisfied with their job and portrayed a 'positive' image of detentions and their activities: *"it is really the case that they are treated with as much dignity and respect as possible. I find it hard to see how anything could be done even better, really"* (D2). However, several problems were also spelled out during the interviews, yet mostly indirectly.

The Swedish detention system suffers from fundamental implementation gaps between policy objectives and operational realities. A recent reorganization intended to improve efficiency in the Swedish detention (and return) infrastructures has instead exacerbated systemic problems, as one staff member noted: *"It was part of a major reorganisation... that was supposed to lead to some form of efficiency improvement. But we have seen that it has been the exact opposite"* (D3). Staff reported that administrative tasks, such as scanning documents and writing case notes—previously handled by specialized caseworkers—were transferred to frontline supervisors, creating operational bottlenecks. While some praised the decentralization of administrative competence (*"mostly for the better"*), others highlighted how standardization ignored local workflows:

"Our detention centre was well-functioning. After reorganization, it became a broken boat—putting out fires while water kept pouring in... And then we have gone from being a cheap, well-functioning detention centre... Schematically, we have become a very expensive detention centre in operation" (D4).

This reorganization, intended to standardize procedures, has instead generated new inefficiencies while failing to address core systemic issues. As a staff member noted with palpable frustration, *"We need even more training in motivational interviewing... conflict management, threats and violence [response]... To work on how we should not be influenced by the person who is shouting and upset"* (D1). These gaps in staff preparedness reveal how policy changes often outpace practical implementation.

The system faces significant security dilemmas due to legal constraints. As a detention officer explained:

"We are not allowed to search visitors who come in. But they are changing that a little bit now. Drugs come in, of course. Because we don't have the ability to stop it, we're not allowed to search, we're not even allowed to ask for identification. And the media also like to write about drugs"

flowing freely or things like that. But they forget to say that the legislation says that we are not allowed to". (D2)

This tension between maintaining security and respecting rights creates what one officer called "a grey area" that ultimately compromises both objectives. However, on the ground staff face cumbersome protocols for basic security measures, such as body searches: *"Each search requires a signed decision, witness corroboration, and digital archiving. Under time pressure, we sometimes skip it—which risks safety"* (D4). This bureaucratic burden contrasts sharply with police and prison services, where streamlined protocols exist. A common pattern emerging from the interviews was that detention staff compare their facility and role with the Police and PPS. Some argue for more securitization of the space:

"I myself don't understand how difficult it can be to actually get a drug dog here. You could do it maybe. Two or three times a year. Because then people also notice that occasionally something actually comes here." (D2)

Sweden's approach to detention stands apart from most EU counterparts in a fundamental way. While other countries assign detention operations to police or prison authorities, Sweden tasks its migration agency with both administrative decision-making and running detention centres - a dual role that frontline staff say has become increasingly untenable. *"There's an incredible amount to streamline,"* admits one detention manager (D4), *"but even with improvements, we'll still lack critical tools to operate safely and effectively."* This systemic tension became starkly apparent as Sweden's detention facilities evolved from reception-like environments to high-security operations. According to the same manager, this shift created an expertise gap that the agency began recruiting staff from the prison service.

From the perspective of detention staff, three critical gaps can be identified in the detention infrastructures: The *first* one is legal limitations. Unlike prison authorities, detention staff cannot conduct routine searches or confiscate contraband without cumbersome paperwork. The *second* one is training deficit. The detention staff is not ready to handle the more securitized situation. Officers lack proper training in security protocols and de-escalation techniques needed for today's more volatile environment, as stressed by several of the staff interviewed. The *final* one can be seen like a 'identity crisis'. The agency struggles to balance its original administrative purpose with its new security responsibilities.

A core implementation gap exists between the official rhetoric of voluntary return and its practical execution. Despite the emphasis on motivational techniques, staff acknowledge that *"the majority of returns are ultimately carried out by the Police as forced returns."* This discrepancy reveals systemic contradictions in Sweden's approach to migration management. The legal framework compounds these issues through inconsistent decision-making. As one lawyer observed: *"You can have two decisions where one has been approved and the other rejected, and you can't really understand why. And that has to do with the fact that it is so vague."* This unpredictability undermines both efficiency and fairness in the system.

The detention of vulnerable groups presents particularly acute implementation challenges. Staff express moral distress, *emotional labour* about detaining children and pregnant women, with one officer stating: *"I think it's a blot on Swedish migration policy... it's not the children's fault that the parents may have made a mess of things"* (D2). These ethical concerns highlight tensions between policy objectives and humanitarian principles.

Implementation gaps in Sweden's detention infrastructure reveal systemic inefficiencies and ethical dilemmas that undermine the intended goals of return migration policies. One significant barrier is the lack of incentives for receiving countries to cooperate, as highlighted by Delmi: *"What does this country have to gain from cooperating with Sweden in this respect? If there is nothing to gain, then the very point of them actually co-operating falls by the wayside."* Delmi highlights that without tangible benefits, these countries are less likely to assist with the return process. Giving the example that countries like Georgia, which seek closer ties with the EU, exhibit higher cooperation levels due to perceived benefits. In contrast, countries like India, viewing the return of a few nationals as inconsequential, show minimal cooperation. Receiving countries' unwillingness to cooperate (e.g., refusing travel documents) renders detention ineffective, yet alternatives are rarely explored. This absence of cooperation exacerbates delays and leaves individuals in prolonged limbo, complicating efforts to enforce deportations. Coordination challenges within bureaucratic systems further compound these issues, with time-consuming processes such as obtaining travel documents creating additional obstacles. Detention staff and CSOs alike emphasize how procedural delays often render detention ineffective, as noted by a lawyer: *"As long as living as an undocumented migrant in Sweden provides better life opportunities than going home, people simply will not voluntarily return."*

Humanitarian concerns add another layer of complexity. Migrants often fear returning to their home countries due to potential threats to their safety and well-being. Save the Children points out the social and psychological strain faced by individuals trapped in prolonged uncertainty: *"We meet many people who have been in Sweden for a very, very long time in a very vulnerable situation without really any major social protection."* This underscores systemic failures in addressing the human costs of detention policies.

Our lawyer respondent sheds light on another gap, namely the inconsistencies within legal decision-making in asylum cases. One major issue is the ambiguity in interpreting what constitutes persecution and the severity required for protection. The lawyer explains, *"You can have two decisions where one has been approved and the other rejected, and you can't really understand why. And that has to do with the fact that it is so vague."* This inconsistency undermines the legal certainty required for fair adjudication. Such unpredictability undermines trust in the system and creates a fragile legal framework susceptible to political influences. As the lawyer states, *"We have a principle. If we follow it to the letter, it might mean that 95 per cent of all Afghans must be granted a residence permit in Sweden. No, that's not possible. It can't be like that. So, then we start to do different things, which means that these principles lose their legal independence"* (L1). This, in practice, leads to a fragile legal framework where decisions can appear arbitrary and influenced by external factors, rather than grounded in consistent legal principles.

Additionally, Caritas highlights the broader socio-political implications of restrictive migration policies. The organization criticizes the policy frameworks for not considering the realities of migration and for being overly focused on curbing irregular migration without addressing the underlying causes. Caritas argues, *"All these restrictive, inhumane laws and policies will not succeed. Europe will not succeed. We can make migrants' lives miserable. The only winner will be the criminals who can organise, use the gap that exists."* FARR adds another layer of complexity by highlighting the ambiguity in defining cooperation between migrants and authorities: The organization notes that the criteria for what constitutes

“cooperation” (referring to counselling sessions) with the Migration Agency are often unclear and subjective. This ambiguity can lead to situations where migrants believe they are cooperating, yet are still considered non-compliant by the authorities. FARR describes a scenario where an individual maintained at a known address, received support from the SMA, attended return interviews, and actively sought assistance from embassies, yet was still deemed “*uncooperative*”. This lack of a clear and consistent definition of ‘cooperation’ creates confusion and can result in unfair outcomes, where migrants who make genuine efforts to comply with procedures are still penalized. Another aspect highlighted by CSO representatives was the limited scope of psychosocial support for detainees to process trauma or prepare for reintegration, which in turn exacerbates their distress. In order to fill in this gap, several CSOs (like Red Cross, FARR, Stadsmission) provide support in detentions.

Another source for inefficiency mentioned by the detention staff interviewed was repeated counselling sessions without results. “*They had four, five, six and seven return counsellings. It was like, please, can’t you go home?*” (D3). Several staff, comparing their methods with the Police and suggested a similar clarity in counselling sessions. However, CSO representatives and the lawyer interviewed highlighted the absence of an independent legal counsel during critical interviews, leaving detainees vulnerable (L1).

To conclude this section, the discrepancy between the intended function of detention centres and their practical operation reveals a critical gap. While the official aim is to encourage voluntary returns through dialogue and support, staff admit that most returns are ultimately enforced. As one staff member explained, “*You put him in a detention centre... And you know that he won’t go home,*” underscoring the futility of detaining individuals who cannot be deported. This mismatch between policy goals and enforcement realities highlights a broader issue where detention centres serve more as holding facilities than spaces for promoting voluntary departure.

Overall, these examples highlight the complexities and challenges in the return migration infrastructure. Legal uncertainties, ineffective policy frameworks, and unclear definitions of cooperation contribute to significant implementation gaps. These gaps are exacerbated not only by flawed actions but equally by strategic *inactions*—systemic failures to address known problems despite their recognition. Drawing on interviews with detention staff, CSOs, and legal experts, this analysis identifies how both *commission* and *omission* shape detention outcomes. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach, including clearer legal standards, more humane and realistic policies, and better-defined cooperation criteria to ensure fair and effective outcomes in the return process.

6. Conclusion

This report has provided an in-depth examination of Sweden’s Return Migration Infrastructures, highlighting the key drivers, dynamics, and outcomes from a relational perspective. Additionally, by focusing on detention centres as key sites of return enforcement, the study offered a comprehensive overview of return governance through an infrastructural theoretical framework, mapping the governance actors, their interconnections, actions/inactions, and the methods, materials, and resources they employ, as well as how they align, facilitate, or obstruct return practices.

Sweden's approach to returns is shaped by competing imperatives of efficiency, legality, and humanitarianism (Malm Lindberg, 2023). However, the recent political shift toward restrictive migration policies has disrupted this balance, reframing returns not as a measure of last resort but as a central pillar of migration control. This recalibration has elevated enforcement objectives while marginalizing humanitarian considerations, embedding returns within a populist narrative that increasingly portrays detention and deportation as punitive mechanisms.

RMIs in Sweden, while exhibiting certain functional similarities and collaborative harmonization efforts (cf. Germany see van Leerkes & Houte, 2020) with practices from other EU member states, are distinctly governed and structured. The unique characteristics of Sweden, along with its corporatist state-society legacy, have fostered a balanced approach and a consensus regarding the legal framework that oversees RMIs. This results in a highly governmentalized domain characterized by top-down governance strategies, with the SMA serving as the linchpin of this system, overseeing detention, assisted voluntary return (AVR), and enforcement in collaboration with the Border Police and detention authorities. This centralized model has fostered an institutionalized and ostensibly efficient deportation apparatus, yet one that simultaneously grows more complex and opaque. The emphasis on efficiency poses a risk of establishing a professionalized deportation system, effectively transforming migrants into deportable objects.

Our research identifies four categories of return along a spectrum of voluntariness: voluntary repatriation, self-managed returns, assisted voluntary returns, and forced removals. These categories are fluid rather than fixed, with overlaps that expose the constructed nature of "voluntary" compliance. A key finding is the critical role of case officers and detention staff, whose discretionary assessments and unmonitored interactions create grey zones of informality. Two practices (doings) within RMIs in particular shape these ambiguities, ultimately shaping the scope and direction of RMIs in practice:

- *Case officers' individual assessments*: Case officers wield significant interpretive authority through individualized assessments that lack transparent oversight mechanisms. This creates a governance grey area where inconsistent applications of policy and subjective judgments produce trajectorial outcomes for migrants. The absence of transparent monitoring systems for the assessments conducted by case officers results in a grey area, leading to inconsistencies and a lack of legal clarity. Moreover, these informalities - revealed as communicative technologies of power - cultivate a certain governmentality of voluntariness/cooperation vs coercion.
- *Return counselling – motivational interviews*: As outlined in the report, these interviews - ostensibly designed to encourage voluntary compliance - operate through informal, unmonitored interactions that mask coercive underpinnings. They significantly influence a migrant's willingness to comply with the return decision and their availability to authorities. Throughout various stages of the return process, case officers and detention personnel conduct motivational interviews to assess the migrants' cooperative attitudes. They employ psychological pressure (e.g., conditional incentives and implied threats of harsher enforcement) while being framed as neutral counselling.

The relationship between CSOs and RMIs presents a notable paradox. While most Swedish CSOs maintain critical policy positions against current return and detention regimes, their operational engagement with RMIs remains *limited*, shaped by institutional and

infrastructural constraints. This dynamic has contributed to the governmentalization of return governance, where CSOs participate only when explicitly invited, leaving little room for systemic challenge. Nevertheless, even within these narrow parameters, CSOs continue to play a meaningful - if circumscribed - role in mitigating the system's harshest impacts.

Another notable finding of this study pertains to the use of voluntariness in return practices. The report refers to *enforced voluntary returns* to highlight the coercive elements present in practices which transforms choice into compliance. The concept of voluntariness is a tricky, ambiguous concept. The report refers to "enforced voluntary returns" to highlight the coercive elements present in practices that are ostensibly voluntary. This ambiguity surrounding the idea of voluntary return contributes to a lack of formality. Additionally, we scrutinized the use of the term "assisted" in conjunction with voluntary and forced returns, as it frequently implies limited and conditional support during the pre-return phase, while post-return assistance is largely outsourced to non-governmental organizations and international entities in the countries of origin.

Detention centres constitute a primary node within Sweden's return migration infrastructure (RMI), serving as key sites where the coercive continuum between forced removal and enforced voluntariness becomes most materially apparent. The *dynamic security* model – prioritizing staff presence over physical restraints— projects an image of *benign* custody while enforcing rigid control. Everyday practices, from structured activities to monitored interactions, sustain an illusion of normalcy, yet their underlying purpose remains unchanged: to ensure migrant availability for removal. This system operates through what we term *enforced voluntariness*, where choice is structured through constrained alternatives and resistance is neutralized through everyday routines.

Furthermore, the research, albeit in a limited capacity, examined the function of *return liaison officers* within RMIs, and sought to comprehend their methodologies in facilitating returns through the lens of extraterritorial migration management strategies. This aspect can also be analysed as a novel form of return diplomacy, which is executed through local and sectoral networks in an ad hoc fashion.

An important dimension not fully explored in this report concerns how RMIs extend their reach to irregularized migrants through social exclusion mechanisms. As Leerkes and van Houte (2020) demonstrate, this expanded scope implicates a wider network of actors beyond traditional migration authorities. Irregularization systematically strips individuals of fundamental rights - including access to legal counsel, employment, housing, social welfare, and healthcare - effectively transforming Sweden's welfare state into an apparatus of border control. This exclusionary regime operates through diffuse governance, where frontline professionals across social services (medical practitioners, educators, housing officials, municipal agents, and employers) become unwitting participants in migration enforcement, collectively reinforcing the infrastructure of removal through their everyday decisions and interactions.

In conclusion, the return infrastructures in Sweden represent a complex network that includes not only highly institutionalized and formal governance actors, but also non-governmental organizations, experts, private service providers, and a diverse array of public authorities as well as also materials, technologies, procedural steps, and places. Ultimately, Sweden's RMIs reflect not just migration governance in practice, but a broader reconfiguration of state power in an era of restrictive migration control regimes and border politics.

7. References

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